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MArInE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D2.1

Report on the characterization of major sources of marine litter and macro-plastic in the demo sites

30/06/2021

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Executive Summary

The MAELSTROM project aims to test and evaluate innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in different coastal environments, while also assessing their impact on the ecosystems in selected demo sites and evaluating the economic and societal benefits of the MAELSTROM solutions within local economies. The Deliverable 2.1 - Report on the characterization of major sources of marine litter and macro-plastic in the demo sites, aimed to create the baseline knowledge about marine litter sources both land and sea-based. An overall review on marine litter sources, in particular macro-plastic, was performed at European level. The review was based on information available from literature and the results served as reference to frame the results of the specific literature surveys focused on the two demo sites. In the two demo sites, i.e the Lagoon of Venice and the North Western coast of Portugal, detailed studies focused on the identification and mapping of the sources of macroplastic were analysed. In particular, information about mass flow and about the characteristics of the macro-plastics was collected to identify their potential sources and pathways. The survey was performed through the consultation and analysis of existing databases on marine litter data on the sea floor, rivers and beaches. This allowed to organize the marine litter data available for demo sites upon spatial layers to support the comparison with the applied dispersal numerical models. The collected information and data will feed the numerical models run in T2.2.

MAELSTROM

Table of Content

Executive Summary	4
1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project	11
2 MAELSTROM Consortium	12
3 Aim of the Deliverable	13
4 General introduction on ML issue	14
4.1 Definition of sources and pathways	15
4.2 The challenge in identifying and quantifying sources	17
4.2.1 Sources and transport pathways of microplastics	18
4.2.2 Sources and transport pathways of marine litter	19
5 Analysis on European level	21
5.1 Most common litter found in rivers	21
5.2 Most common litter found on the beach	27
5.3 Most common litter found on the seafloor	31
6 Focus on North East Atlantic region	35
6.1 Reported amount of beach litter	35
6.2 Reported amount of seafloor litter	38
7 Focus on Mediterranean region	41
7.1 Most likely sources of marine litter	43
7.1.1 Pathways: watershed and rivers	45
7.2 Reported amount and type of litter found on the beach and on the sea-floor	50
7.2.1 Beach litter	50
7.2.2 Seafloor litter	53
8 The Adriatic Sea	58
8.1 Sources of ML in the Adriatic	58
8.2 Macrolitter on beaches and seafloor in the Adriatic	62
8.2.1 Beach litter	62
8.2.2 Seafloor litter	65
9 Marine Litter on the NW Portuguese Coast and Estuaries	69

MAELSTROM

9.1	Plastics and Microplastics	74
9.2	Anthropogenic pressures in the Ave estuary (MAELSTROM Portuguese demonstration site, NW Portugal)	76
10	The Venice demo site: analysis of available data on beach and seabed litter in the Venice lagoon and Venetian coastal area	79
10.1	Description of the study area	79
10.2	Beach litter	82
10.2.1	Methodologies	82
10.2.2	Results and Discussion	85
10.3	Seabed litter	92
10.3.1	Methodologies	92
10.3.2	Results and Discussion	93
11	Conclusions	98
12	References	102
	Annexes	109

List of Figures

<i>Figure 1 - Land-based sources of primary and secondary microplastics and pathways to the ocean (Source: UNEP, 2016).</i>	18
<i>Figure 2 - Sources and pathways of marine litter (original by J.M. Veiga, Deltares).</i>	19
<i>Figure 3 - Sources and pathways of some key marine litter items (Source: Veiga et al, 2016).</i>	20
<i>Figure 4 - RIMMEL and RiLON data collection - rivers and monitoring sites (color coded by Regional Sea). Source: González-Fernández et al., 2018.</i>	21
<i>Figure 5 - Spatial distribution of annual inputs of riverine floating macrolitter (items/year) into the sea based on mean-based modelled estimates. Source: González-Fernández et al., 2021.</i>	23
<i>Figure 6 - Riverine floating macrolitter fluxes (items/h) (a) and annual loads (b) in 42 rivers in 11 European and non-European countries, between 2016 and 2017. Source: González-Fernández et al., 2021.</i>	24
<i>Figure 7 - Top 10 items reported per regional sea, reported via the Marine Litter Watch App. Source: EEA, 2018.</i>	29
<i>Figure 8 - Seafloor marine litter densities in the Mediterranean and other European Seas. Source: Ioakeimidis et al. 2017.</i>	32

<i>Figure 9 - Trends in the average number of items of marine litter collected on reference beaches in three- month periods in the OSPAR regions. Source: OSPAR Quality Status Report 2010.....</i>	<i>37</i>
<i>Figure 10 - Composition of marine litter according to main litter types for the period 2014-2015 in the OSPAR Maritime Area. Source: OSPAR Intermediate Assessment, 2017.....</i>	<i>38</i>
<i>Figure 11 - Relative number of litter items per km² of the seafloor across the Greater North Sea, Celtic Seas and the Eastern Bay of Biscay, based on the number of items caught as by-catch in fisheries trawls. Source: OSPAR Intermediate Assessment, 2017.....</i>	<i>40</i>
<i>Figure 12 - Plastic accumulated in the different compartments of the Mediterranean Sea. The three values for each box represent the low/central/high estimates. The central estimate is displayed as a full blue square and labelled with bold font. Values shown in metric tonnes. Seafloor plastic includes both the microplastics trapped in sediments and macroplastics deposited on the seafloor. Source: Boucher and Bilard 2020.....</i>	<i>42</i>
<i>Figure 13 - Mediterranean Sea – Macro-litter in rivers: top 10 items list.....</i>	<i>46</i>
<i>Figure 14 - Total annual macroplastic and microplastic leakage into the Mediterranean Sea using three estimates (low, medium and high). Source: Boucher and Bilard, 2020.....</i>	<i>46</i>
<i>Figure 15 - Leakage of macroplastic from mismanaged waste into the Mediterranean Sea, watershed view. For presentation purposes, the countries upstream of the Nile river are not shown. They are responsible for 9% of the total leakage. Source: Boucher and Bilard, 2020... </i>	<i>47</i>
<i>Figure 16 - Leakage of macroplastic from mismanaged waste into the Mediterranean Sea, per locality view. Source: Boucher and Bilard, 2020.....</i>	<i>48</i>
<i>Figure 17 - Characterization of beach litter from 23 sites along the Mediterranean coastline (Source: Vlachogianni et al., 2020).....</i>	<i>51</i>
<i>Figure 18 - Characterization of beach litter from 56 sites along the western Mediterranean coast of Spain (Alicante province). Source: Asensio-Montesinos et al. 2019.....</i>	<i>52</i>
<i>Figure 19 - Composition of litter items (a) number of items and percentage of total collected items; (b) weight of items in kg and percentage of total weight of collected items from beach litter surveys on the Mediterranean Moroccan coastline (Source: Driss et al. 2017).....</i>	<i>53</i>
<i>Figure 20 - Bubble plot of plastic data by haul from the MEDITS surveys of 2013, 2014 and 2015; for each haul an average value among the three years is shown (Source: Spedicato et al. 2019).....</i>	<i>56</i>
<i>Figure 21 - Map of the model predictions of plastic density on the seafloor in the norther Mediterranean basin. Density thresholds to identify hotspot areas are indicated in the legend in correspondence to the 85°, 90° and 95° percentiles of the raster data. Source: Spedicato et al. (2019).....</i>	<i>57</i>
<i>Figure 22 - Figure x Sources of marine litter on the basis of aggregated results at the national level and at the Adriatic & Ionian level (Source: Vlachogianni et al. 2018).....</i>	<i>59</i>
<i>Figure 23 - Percentages of items belonging to three different sources categories: land-based, sea-based and mixed (Source: Vlachogianni et al. 2018).....</i>	<i>60</i>

<i>Figure 24 - Spatial distribution of the floating debris inputs into the Adriatic Basin: shipping lanes (gray scatter plot); rivers (open blue diamonds), the largest rivers (closed blue circles); cities (open red circles); and the largest cities (closed red circles) (Source: Liubartseva et al., 2016).</i>	62
<i>Figure 25 Spatial distribution of beach litter densities for the 31 beaches (Source: Vlachogianni et al. 2018).</i>	63
<i>Figure 26 - Beach litter densities on an aggregated basis at the national level (Croatia is on the secondary y-axis). Whiskers indicate the interquartile ranges, the black dots denote the median values (Source Vlachogianni et al., 2018).</i>	64
<i>Figure 27 - Top-ten items of the Italian Adriatic beaches (Source: Vlachogianni et al., 2018).</i>	65
<i>Figure 28 - Spatial distribution and composition of benthic litter. Spatial distribution of the total litter collected on the sea floor (A) and total marine litter composition in terms of numbers (B) and weight (C) (Source: Pasquini et al., 2016).</i>	66
<i>Figure 29 - Spatial distribution and weight of the total litter collected on the sea bottom (Source: Strafella et al., 2019).</i>	67
<i>Figure 30 - Seafloor litter composition in the Adriatic sea (Source: Stafella et al., 2019).</i>	68
<i>Figure 31 - Average concentration of macroplastics and microplastics on beaches, offshore seabed and seawater reported in continental Portugal classified in four classes of concentrations (source: Prata et al. 2020).</i>	70
<i>Figure 32 - Floating marine debris kernel density map. Kernel density estimates are presented in equal intervals of 10% increments, with warmer tones representing the higher concentration areas (10%). North sector and South sector (source: Sá et al. (2016)).</i>	71
<i>Figure 33 - Percentages of the different sources accounting for Top 20 items of beach litter.</i>	74
<i>Figure 34 - Percentages of the different sources accounting for litter items found on the seabed.</i>	74
<i>Figure 35 - Location of Ave River basin and identification of potential litter sources.</i>	77
<i>Figure 36 - Map showing some of the main land-based sources of marine litter (i.e. rivers, cities and touristic beaches) and aquaculture farms (i.e. mussel farm) for the area of the Northern Adriatic.</i>	80
<i>Figure 37 - Maps showing the density of maritime traffic in the northern Adriatic related to cargos, passenger ships and fishing vessels.</i>	81
<i>Figure 38 - Beaches monitored over time for marine litter along the Venetian coastline.</i>	82
<i>Figure 39 - Mean values of items found in the monitored beaches.</i>	86
<i>Figure 40 - Relative abundance of each of the top ten categories in some monitored beaches.</i>	88
<i>Figure 41 - PCA performed with a data set including the top ten of IT categories found in the monitored beaches. Factor 1 showed significant positive loadings of the variables IT 7,12, 18, 19 and 53; Factor 2 showed significant positive loading of the variable IT51.</i>	89

Figure 42 - Relative abundances of each litter source calculated on the whole dataset and n. of items found for each source.	89
Figure 43 - Abundances of items according to their sources in each monitored beach over time.....	90
Figure 44 - Relative abundances of each material composing the litter items calculated on the whole dataset and n. of items found for each material.....	91
Figure 45 - Localization of the 32 stations monitored for the presence of seabed litter.	92
Figure 46 - Detailed information for each of the 4 surveys performed to monitor seabed litter.....	92
Figure 47 - Total amount of marine litter items monitored in each station.....	94
Figure 48 - Most represented G categories.....	94
Figure 49 - Relative abundances of each litter source calculated on the whole dataset and n. of items found for each source.	96
Figure 50 - Abundances of items according to their sources in each monitored station.....	96
Figure 51 - PCA performed with a matrix made of a data set including the top 10 of G categories found in the monitored stations. Factor 1 showed significant negative loadings of the variables G10, G124, G2, G6, G67 and G79; Factor 2 significant positive loadings of the variables G134, G45 and G51.	97

List of Tables

Table 1 - Top items in European rivers (aggregated results from RIMMEL surveys of floating litter, 2016-2017). Source: González-Fernández et al., 2021.....	22
Table 2 - Top items in regional rivers (aggregated results from RIMMEL surveys of floating litter, 2016-2017). Source: González-Fernández et al., 2018.....	26
Table 3 - Top items from beach litter surveys (100m) published in studies at European-, regional sea- or basin-level. Numbers indicate the rank in the top list. Colored items indicate incidence in at least 40% of the top 10 lists considered. Note: Caution must be taken when comparing these results, as surveys do not always use the same items categories. (*) some surveys may account also for plastic straws under this category; (**) rank is probably underestimated, as some surveys do not account for this category; (***) includes also drink bottles where volume was not specified; (****) may also include plastic drink bottles.....	28
Table 4 - Type of litter items and most likely sources from beach litter surveys in study-sites in the four regional seas.....	30
Table 5 - Top litter items recorded in seafloor surveys in European regional seas.....	33
Table 6 - Macro-litter in Mediterranean rivers: top 20 items list.	45
Table 7 - The top 10 contributing localities and the total leakage into the Mediterranean Sea. Source: Boucher and Bilard, 2020.	49

MAELSTROM

<i>Table 8 - Top fifteen beach litter items for the Mediterranean Sea and their share and average frequency per 100 m coast line (UNEP/MAP, 2017).</i>	51
<i>Table 9 - Litter abundance on the seafloor in the Mediterranean sea (items/km²), where not differently specified. Source: Updated from Ioakeimidis et al. (2017).</i>	55
<i>Table 10 - Plastic abundance (%) lying on the seafloor of the Mediterranean Sea. Source: UNEP/MAP (2017).</i>	56
<i>Table 11 - Top 10 marine litter inputs into the Adriatic Basin estimated (Source: Liubarseva et al., 2016).</i>	61
<i>Table 12 - Summary of the studies across marine litter in NW Portuguese coastal area.</i>	69
<i>Table 13. The top 20 items list in the North Western Portuguese beaches compiled using data from 2010 to 2020 (https://www.emodnet.eu) and relative sources according to Table, 2 Annex 1).</i>	72
<i>Table 14 - Sea bottom trawled litter in the North-western coast of Portugal (data from 2010 to 2020, https://www.emodnet.eu) and relative sources according to Table 2, Annex 1.</i>	73
<i>Table 15 - Number of plastic debris recorded in beach sediments in the north coast of Portugal (Source: Martins and Sobral, 2011).</i>	75
<i>Table 16 - Abundance and diversity of microplastics recorded in the Matosinhos beach during autumn and spring between 2011 and 2012 (Source: Antunes et al, 2018).</i>	75
<i>Table 17 - Estimated Ave River basin macrolitter (FML) annual loading (Source: González-Fernández et al. (2021)).</i>	78
<i>Table 18 - Beaches monitored along the Venetian coastline: location, sampling dates and data source.</i>	83
<i>Table 19 - Mean values, maximum and minimum values, standard deviations and cv for each sampling sites.</i>	86
<i>Table 20 - Top ten of the IT categories showing the highest number of items considering all the sampling sites and periods.</i>	87
<i>Table 21 - Top ten list of the G categories showing the highest number of items considering all the sampling stations.</i>	95

MAELSTROM

1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex question to the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy. MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions providing also a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) enhances social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

MAELSTROM

2 MAELSTROM Consortium

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MAELSTROM

3 Aim of the Deliverable

The aim of this Deliverable is to give an overall review about marine litter (ML) typology and most likely sources, both land and sea bases, at European level, with special attention on macroplastic. The results of this review serve as reference to frame the results of the specific surveys focused on the demo sites. In Venice (IT) and in the coastal area of near Porto (PT), detailed studies for the identification and mapping of the ML sources were considered.

The literature survey includes existing databases on ML data on the water column, sea floor, estuaries, rivers and beaches. Specifically, the European/Regional Seas review is based on existing publications (scientific papers and “grey” literature) while the study areas review is based on existing publications and raw data, when available.

The review intends to provide the knowledge-base on the characteristics, sources and pathways of marine litter, necessary to inform MAELSTROM Work Packages and particularly the modelling of ML in the two demo sites of the lagoon of Venice (Italy) and the Ave River estuary (Portugal). Specifically, the review aims at:

- improving the understanding of the amounts and types of ML occurring in Europe and in particular in the study areas;
- improving the understanding of the main sources and pathways (e.g. rivers) of ML in Europe and in particular in the study areas;
- supporting the definition of the input data and assumptions related to ML to be used in numerical models of ML spatial distribution.

To achieve this objective, we assume the following constraints:

- the main focus is on macro-litter
- the review has a geographic scope focussed on the study sites
- ML literature has been analysed to indicate the most probable sources and amount (inc. sea floor litter and riverine litter).

4 General introduction on ML issue

Anthropogenic waste ending up in the marine environment has been recognized to have various potentially harmful implications on marine ecosystems and human activities at seas. Marine litter, defined as “any persistent, manufactured or processed solid material discarded, disposed of or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment”, consists of a wide range of materials, including but not limited to plastic, glass, metal, paper and wood. However, approximately 60 % to 80% of the world marine litter is made of plastic (Derriak, 2002).

Plastic is constituted by synthetic and semi-synthetic polymers that can persist for long period in the natural environment. Due to its low production cost, high malleability and high resistance to chemicals, temperature and light, from the middle of the last century plastic material started to be used in several sectors. For these reasons, plastic production rose considerably. In 2019, global plastics production almost reached 370 million tonnes, whereas in Europe, it reached 58 million tonnes. Packaging, building and construction and automotive are the three main markets of plastics amounting respectively for 40%, 20% and 10% of the total plastic demand [Plastics Europe, 2020]. The same properties that make plastics so useful also make them a significant environmental threat, mainly due to their inappropriate management once they become waste. It was estimated that about 10% of this waste ends up in the oceans (Ryan et al., 2009). Due to their various impacts and long persistence on the marine environment, plastics are considered emerging contaminants of growing concern, potentially affecting human health.

Based on the items most often collected, it is commonly estimated that the majority of marine litter derives from land-based sources (i.e. 80%). The most collected items are waste deriving from consumer products or their packaging, such as food wrappers, drink bottles, bottle caps and grocery bags (International Coastal Cleanup, 2018). However, sea-based sources can sometimes be dominant in some regions, depending on the level of human activities developed at sea in the area such as shipping, fisheries and offshore installations (Galgani et al., 2015). Once in the marine environment, marine litter can be found in all marine compartments: sea surface, water column, seafloor, coastline and biota. Marine debris is commonly found at the sea surface or washed up on shorelines, and much of the work on marine litter has focussed on coastal areas. Floating litter items can be transported by the currents until they sink to the seafloor, be deposited on the shore or degrade over time

MAELSTROM

(Andrady, 2015). Floating litter is mainly composed of plastic items with lower density than seawater mainly made of polyethylene and polypropylene. Their low density facilitates dispersion by currents and winds, sometimes travelling long distances from source areas. They can be washed ashore or sink to the seafloor due to the increase in their density because of the fouling of organic matter and / or marine organisms. It is estimated that for a large proportion of the global marine litter the final accumulation place is the seafloor (Consoli et al., 2018). Change in the nature, presence or abundance of anthropogenic debris on the seafloor is much less widely investigated than sea surface patterns (Galvani et al., 2015).

4.1 Definition of sources and pathways

To address marine litter issue, it is crucial not only to monitor its presence, abundance and fate in the various marine compartments, but also to identify the sources and pathways that lead to its presence at sea. Analysis of marine litter items can provide some clues to their origins. However, this task can be difficult to achieve since the same item could derive from different sources and activities and also could be transported over long distances from its geographical origin.

In the JRC Technical Report "Identifying Sources of Marine Litter" (Veiga et al. 2016), the term source of marine litter is used to define the economic sector or human activity from which litter originates, also identifying the reasons why a given item leaves the intended cycle and/or enters the natural or urban environment and becomes a problem. Consequently, the geographic origin can be defined by the geographic location of the source.

The analysis of the human activities causing marine litter is a key element to identify the responses to prevent it. The three main activities that determine the release of plastic items to the environment and into the ocean are the improper management of waste and residues, intentional littering of industrial, commercial or domestic waste and accidental and unintentional littering.

At European level, marine litter has received particular attention after its inclusion as one of the eleven Descriptors within the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD – European Directive 2008/56/EC). The main objective of the MSFD has been to achieve a Good Environmental Status (GES) for the European waters by 2020. The Descriptor 10 contemplates that properties and quantities of marine litter does not cause harm to the coastal and marine environment. Consequently, all the European

MAELSTROM

countries having marine waters should have reduced pollution deriving from marine litter by 2020. Even if the GES was not achieved (Fortibuoni et al. 2021), the knowledge of the quantities of litter in European seas, the fate of litter in the marine environment and the potentially harmful biological, physical and chemical effects on habitats is improved in recent years.

Specifically, the marine regions covered by the MSFD are the Baltic Sea, the North-east Atlantic Ocean, the Mediterranean Sea and the Black Sea. The MSFD recommends to use the existing regional institutional cooperation structures, such as those under the Regional Sea Conventions (RSCs), in order to achieve coherence and coordination in their strategies and policies developed to protect the marine environment [Monitoring Guidance for Marine Litter in European Seas. MSFD GES Technical Subgroup on Marine Litter (TSG-ML)]. Consequently, the Regional Sea Conventions implemented coordinated monitoring programmes and perform joint assessments of the state of the environment to evaluate the presence and impacts of marine litter:

- HELCOM Regional Action Plan for Marine Litter (2015) set the standard for each of the nine Baltic Sea countries to minimize the effects of marine litter.
- Black Sea Marine Litter Regional Action Plan (2018) that consolidated and implemented environmental strategies and measures for a sustainable integrated management of marine litter in the Black Sea region.
- OSPAR Regional Action Plan for Prevention and Management of Marine Litter in the North-East Atlantic (2014) set out the policy context to prevent and reduce marine litter pollution and its impact in the North-East Atlantic;
- MEDPOL Regional Plan on Marine Litter Management in the Mediterranean (2014) set out the adoption of legally binding measures to prevent and reduce marine litter pollution in the Mediterranean Basin.

The term “sources” of marine litter and microplastics can be used to refer to distinct concepts and processes. For example, rivers are sometimes referred to as “sources” while they are in fact only the physical transport mechanism of litter or microplastics from another point of origin. As such, it is important to clearly define the terminology used in this review, following the Technical Group on Marine Litter (TGML) recommendations (Veiga et al., 2016) – see Box 1.

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BOX 1

Sources: the economic sector or human activity from which litter originates and leaves the intended cycle or enters the environment, e.g. tourism, agriculture, aquaculture, fisheries, shipping, etc. The means of release of that litter from that source (e.g. littering, fly-tipping, loss, etc.) can be further specified. The likely geographic location of where litter may have originated can also be identified, e.g. an unsanitary landfill, an urban area, a recreational beach. In this case, this will be referred to as geographic origin. This is most often used in transport modelling studies, where the spatial movement of litter is simulated.

Pathways: the physical and/or technical means by which litter enters the marine environment. Examples include, sewage systems and rivers for litter that is transported from inland. Litter can also enter the marine environment via direct input, i.e. discarded or lost directly on the coast or into the sea (e.g. from recreational activities, fishing, shipping).

Land-based sources: terrestrial activities that generate direct inputs of litter onto the coast or into the sea or that generate litter that is then transported into the sea via runoff, rivers, wind, urban or industrial effluents.

Sea-based sources: maritime activities that generate direct inputs of litter into the sea. Examples include, shipping, fishing, offshore installations or dumping at sea.

4.2 The challenge in identifying and quantifying sources

Marine litter and microplastics can originate from a wide variety of different sources. Once accidentally or purposefully released, litter and particles can be mobilised by wind, runoff, rivers, tides and marine currents across environmental compartments and very long distances. In the environment, litter is subject to specific interactions with the surrounding medium and can be retained (e.g. vegetation, sediment), fragment, sink, be ingested or even removed by clean-up operations.

Identifying and quantifying the specific sources that contribute to marine litter and microplastics can be very challenging. Most of the litter items recorded in the environment are not exclusive to one specific economic activity or application, nor a stage of the value chain of products or geographic origin. Moreover, unrecognizable particles or fragments of plastic make it extremely difficult, if not impossible, to identify their possible source (Veiga et al., 2016). As such, to better understand the sources of marine litter and microplastics, there is the need to integrate information and interface with other disciplines, as the processes that generate litter pollution or affect its distribution go beyond the marine domain. As such, studies based on marine and coastal observations are increasingly complemented by geographic and socio-economic data, including on waste management, and supported by tools such

as transport modelling of items/particles in the environment or material flow analyses.

4.2.1 Sources and transport pathways of microplastics

Microplastics can be differentiated in primary or secondary microplastics. Primary microplastics result from manufacturing and usage as microplastic sized particles in the first place (Thompson, 2016). Sources of microplastics include leakages of plastic pellets from the plastic production industry or spillage during transportation but also plastic particles that have been added to cosmetic products and are washed-off during their use. Secondary microplastics, on the other hand, result from the fragmentation of larger items or products, either from waste that is already present in the environment or the weathering of items that are still in use, such as the weathering of tires, textiles and paints (Galafassi et al., 2019). As a result, microplastics can enter the marine environment via sewage networks, runoff and rivers, as well as through atmospheric deposition (Thompson, 2016; Prata, 2018; Galafassi et al, 2019). Worth mentioning that micro (and nano) plastics are globally pervasive in all other environments, from freshwater to soils (Wagner et al, 2014; Chase et al, 2018), as well as in biota (Werner et al, 2016). Figure 1 shows the possible land-based sources and pathways of primary and secondary microplastic to the marine environment. Microplastics can significantly accumulate in sediments. For example, concentrations over 2000 plastic particles per kilogram dry weight have been reported by Vianello et al (2013) in the Venice Lagoon.

Figure 1 - Land-based sources of primary and secondary microplastics and pathways to the ocean (Source: UNEP, 2016).

4.2.2 Sources and transport pathways of marine litter

Marine litter can result from maritime activities at sea (direct input) or from land-based sources. These can be local (e.g. a visitor litters the coast/beach) or more distant inland sources (e.g. illegal dumping or leakages from an unsanitary landfill), from which litter is mobilized by wind and rainfall, and discharged into the sea via runoff and rivers. As such, even non-coastal countries can contribute to marine litter pollution. Figure 2 provides a conceptualization of the key sources and pathways of marine litter.

Figure 2 – Sources and pathways of marine litter (original by J.M. Veiga, Deltares).

As mentioned previously, it is not easy to identify the specific sources and pathways of marine litter based solely on field data. In Figure 3, different sources and pathways are illustrated for four frequently found marine litter items, notably cotton-bud sticks, plastic bags, plastic bottles and fishing nets/lines. While the origin and “route” of some of the items is straightforward (e.g. cotton bud-sticks most likely originate from improper disposal in the toilet, by consumers, and reach the marine environment via sewage), for other items such as plastic bags or bottles, there can be several sources and pathways which are difficult to distinguish. Therefore, the assessment of sources

needs to account for the specific geo-physical and the socio-economic context of the surveyed area. For example, Prevenios et al (2018) assessed the composition and accumulation rates in different beaches in Corfu island, indicating distinct contributions of different sources (e.g. local littering) and pathways (e.g. sea transport/deposition or runoff/wind-blown from local land-based sources), in the different sites. In addition, their analysis revealed that items considered to originate from the same source can arrive at a specific beach from several different pathways.

Figure 3 - Sources and pathways of some key marine litter items (Source: Veiga et al, 2016).

5 Analysis on European level

In this section, we review the most abundant litter items found in the riverine and marine environment in Europe, as well as key regional differences, considering that these differences will reflect contributions of distinct sources.

5.1 Most common litter found in rivers

One of the most extensive and consistent riverine litter data collection done until data in Europe was carried out by the Riverine Litter Observation Network (RiLON), within the RIMMEL project (Riverine and Marine floating macro litter Monitoring and Modelling of Environmental Loading). The initiative involved monthly surveys in 53 rivers in Europe, between June 2016 and September 2017, in the locations shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - RIMMEL and RiLON data collection - rivers and monitoring sites (color coded by Regional Sea). Source: González-Fernández et al., 2018.

The floating litter categorized in detail, enabled to determine the most abundant litter items carried towards the sea (González-Fernández et al., 2018 – Table 1). Plastic

MAELSTROM

composes 82% of the items recorded in the surveys and almost 45% of these are unrecognizable pieces of plastic, including polystyrene. This indicates that a significant amount of plastic pieces originates from fragmentation of larger pieces on land.

Table 1 - Top items in European rivers (aggregated results from RIMMEL surveys of floating litter, 2016-2017). Source: González-Fernández et al., 2021.

Item	% of total items
Plastic pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm, > 50 cm	38.6%
Plastic bottles	9.6%
Plastic cover/packaging	8.4%
Plastic bags	7.8%
Polystyrene pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm, > 50 cm	6.4%
Other paper items	4.0%
Paper packaging	3.6%
Plastic sheets, industrial packaging, plastic sheeting	2.9%
Foam packaging/insulation/polyurethane	2.7%
Metal drink cans	2.1%

The same study aggregates results for rivers discharging in the four regional seas (Table 2). The 60% of the items recorded in rivers discharging into the Atlantic were pieces of plastic and polystyrene, while in other regions these were relatively smaller (approximately 31% for the Mediterranean, 19% in the Black Sea and 4% in the Baltic. Another critical difference is related to nature of use of the items, where the identifiable top items found in Mediterranean rivers are largely packaging products (drink containers, carrier bags) associated to consumer use and disposal, while in other regional rivers items related to industrial activities and transport (e.g. industrial sheeting, crates, wooden pallets, rope) are relatively more abundant.

Regional differences for the NEA and Mediterranean are further discussed in sections 6 and 7, respectively.

Based on the data collected in 42 rivers and streams from 11 countries, González-Fernández et al (2021) analysed the litter flux (as items per hour) and provided a spatial distribution of litter input for different countries and drainage basin sizes based on modelled estimates (Figure 5).

Figure 5 - Spatial distribution of annual inputs of riverine floating macrolitter (items/year) into the sea based on mean-based modelled estimates. Source: González-Fernández et al., 2021.

The results indicate a very large variation of litter fluxes, ranging from 0.1 to 1,459 items/h among the all the rivers. Even within individual rivers the litter fluxes often showed variability between two and three orders of magnitude. In general, the litter fluxes and annual loadings showed decreasing trends towards small basins (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Riverine floating macrolitter fluxes (items/h) (a) and annual loads (b) in 42 rivers in 11 European and non-European countries, between 2016 and 2017. Source: González-Fernández et al., 2021.

MAELSTROM

The authors estimate that most (71.3%) of the riverine items exported from Europe into the sea are transported via small coastal basins (< 100 km²). In addition, their results indicate that countries with long and highly populated coastal areas (e.g. Italy, the United Kingdom, Spain, France and Greece), although with high waste management rates, are among the largest contributors of litter loads into the sea.

KEY MESSAGES

- Similarly to beach litter, plastic pieces and fragments tend to head the top items in floating riverine litter (in number, not mass). There are, however, regional differences, with consumer plastic packaging showing relatively higher expression in Mediterranean rivers than industrial items.
- Floating litter fluxes analysed in European rivers show a broad variation across rivers (0.1 to 1,459 items/h) but also within individual rivers, where the flux often varied between two or three orders of magnitude.
- Small coastal basins seem to discharge most of the riverine litter items exported into the sea. Countries with long and highly populated coastal areas are among the largest contributors of riverine litter loads in Europe.

Table 2 - Top items in regional rivers (aggregated results from RIMMEL surveys of floating litter, 2016-2017). Source: González-Fernández et al., 2018.

Rank	NEA	Baltic Sea	Mediterranean	Black Sea
1	Plastic pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm, > 50 cm	Plastic bottles	Plastic pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm, > 50 cm	Plastic bottles
2	Plastic cover/packaging	Other (metal)	Plastic bottles	Plastic pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm, > 50 cm
3	Polystyrene pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm, > 50 cm	Synthetic rope	Plastic bags	Plastic cover/packaging
4	Plastic bags	Paper packaging	Plastic cover/packaging	Plastic bags
5	Plastic sheets, industrial packaging, plastic sheeting	Plastic bags	Polystyrene pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm, > 50 cm	Plastic crates and containers / baskets
6	Plastic bottles	Other paper items	Other paper items	Paper packaging
7	Foam packaging / insulation / polyurethane	Metal drink cans	Paper packaging	Other paper items
8	Other paper items	Beams / Dunnage	Metal drink cans	Other identifiable plastic items
9	Paper packaging	Plastic pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm, > 50 cm	Foam packaging / insulation / polyurethane	Polystyrene pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm, > 50 cm
10	Other (metal)	Wood pallets	Other identifiable plastic items	Wood pallets

5.2 Most common litter found on the beach

Coastlines are one of the most surveyed compartments in what concerns marine litter pollution, given its accessibility and limited resources needed to collect data. A monitoring programme for beach litter has been ongoing since 2000 in the North East Atlantic area and is regionally coordinated by its regional sea commission - OSPAR. Within this initiative, protocols and guidelines for harmonized surveys have been developed (OSPAR, 2010), and since then have been broadly adopted in Europe.

Beach litter surveys enable the counting and recording of very detailed categories of items, which can help define priorities for intervention in terms of critical litter items, as well as assess trends in their management and leakage into the environment. More important for the scope of this report, detailed beach litter surveys can provide important information about the origin of that litter and the economic activities that may have generated it.

Several peer-reviewed publications and regional reports on beach litter describe the most abundant litter items recorded. Adammo et al (2017) discuss the limitations in aggregating and comparing these results to obtain a Europe-wide output, namely on the fact that the studies relied on different methodologies to calculate or rank the items, as well as classifying items in different categories. In order to obtain a European top list of items, the authors analysed a 2016 pan-European dataset (69 134 surveys from 277 beaches, covering all four EU regional seas), which was collected using a harmonized protocol and list of item categories. In addition to the European list, a rank of top items was generated to each of the main European regional seas (Figure 7). The top beach litter items recorded in European regional surveys and publications are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3 - Top items from beach litter surveys (100m) published in studies at European-, regional sea- or basin-level. Numbers indicate the rank in the top list. Colored items indicate incidence in at least 40% of the top 10 lists considered. Note: Caution must be taken when comparing these results, as surveys do not always use the same items categories. (*) some surveys may account also for plastic straws under this category; (**) rank is probably underestimated, as some surveys do not account for this category; (***) includes also drink bottles where volume was not specified; (****) may also include plastic drink bottles.

item	EEA, 2018	Adammo et al, 2017					Arcadis, 2014			
	EUROPE	EUROPE	NEA	Baltic	MED	Black Sea	North Sea	Baltic	MED	Black Sea
Plastic/polystyrene pieces 2.5cm > < 50 cm	2	1	2	5	3	3	2	1	8	4
Cigarette butts	1	4	7	3	1	2		2	2	1
Plastic caps and lids (drinks, chemicals, plastic rings)		5	4	6	4	1	3	3	3	5
Plastic bags (inc. shopping bags, small plastic bags)	7	10		4	10	5		6	5	7
Crisp packets/sweet wrappers *	8	8	6			10	6		10	2
Cotton bud sticks	6	6	5		5		5		6	
String and cord (diameter less than 1 cm)	9	3	1	9			1	9		
Plastic/polystyrene pieces 0-2.5 cm **	3	2	3		2	8				
Plastic drink bottles ≤ 0.5 l ***	10					7	10		4	3
Other plastic/polystyrene items (identifiable)		9	8	2						
Plastic food containers							9	7		10
Glass /ceramic fragments	4							5		8
Nets and pieces of net > 50 cm					6		8			
Foam sponge					8			4		
Paraffin/wax		7		1						
Glass bottles inc pieces					7				9	
Plastic cups and cup lids	5					9				
Plastic cutlery and straws								8	1	
Other medical items (swabs, bandaging, plaster etc.)			9							
Other sanitary (e.g. diapers, toilet/tissue paper, shaving razors)			10							
Paper (including newspapers, magazines)				7						
Paper cups, food trays, food wrappers, drink containers				8						
Construction material (brick, cement, pipes)				10						
Paper cigarette packets					9					
Plastic drink bottles > 0.5 l						4				
Toys and party poppers						6				
Plastic drink bottles and containers ****										
Mussel/Oyster nets										
Other textiles							4			
Rope							7			
Wood crates								10		
Paper bags									7	
Metal drink cans										6
Other rubber pieces										9

Figure 7 - Top 10 items reported per regional sea, reported via the Marine Litter Watch App. Source: EEA, 2018.

Marine litter composition can show large variations across locations, reflecting the influence of distinct anthropogenic sources. Although there may be differences in litter composition between European regions, it is also evident that such differences can be significant within the region sea basin, a smaller geographic area, such as the Adriatic-Ionian seas (e.g. Fuortibuoni et al, 2019) or even within a country.

A study by Arcadis (van Acoleyen et al., 2014) analysed 343 datasets of beach litter collected between 2012-2013 in Europe (North Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Baltic Sea and Black Sea), and determined the most likely sources of litter for each region, using a likelihood matrix scoring technique (Tudor & Williams, 2004),

as described in Veiga et al. (2016). The analysis indicated that almost 2/3 of the identified litter items originate from consumers, while 20% can be attributed to industrial or professional activities, such as fisheries.

An earlier study (Arcadis, 2012) focused on four study-sites and stakeholder consultation in the regional seas of Europe, has made evident the contribution of distinct sources to the recorded beach litter survey locally (Table 4). Between 36 and 70% of litter corresponds to packaging waste and most litter items (44-90%) are designed to be short-lived/single-use items (Arcadis, 2012).

Table 4 - Type of litter items and most likely sources from beach litter surveys in study-sites in the four regional seas.

Sea (country)	Type of litter items	Most important sources	Reference
NEA (Belgium)	60% use items 36% packaging 4% recreational items	Tourism & recreation (38%) Fishing (12%) Shipping (10%) Ports & harbours (8%)	Arcadis, 2012
Mediterranean (Spain)	51% use items 46% packaging 2% recreational items 1% raw material	Tourism & recreation (41%) Toilet/sanitary (26%) General household (11%) Waste collection & transport (6%)	Arcadis, 2012
Mediterranean (Greece)	Not available	Mismanaged waste on land, tourism & recreation (37 - 62%) Fisheries & aquaculture (5-10%) Sanitary & sewage-related (4-9%) Shipping (1 - 2%) Non-sourced (27-42%)	Prevenios et al, 2017
Baltic Sea (Estonia)	56% packaging 43% use items 1% recreational items	Tourism & recreation (35%) Toilet/sanitary (29%) General household (12%) Waste collection & transport (7%)	Arcadis, 2012

Black Sea (Romania)	70% packaging 28% use items 2% recreational items	Coastal tourism & recreation (58%) General household (20%) Dumpsites/landfills (5%) Construction & demolition (4%)	Arcadis, 2012
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KEY MESSAGES

- Unrecognizable plastic fragments tend to dominate (in number) the litter recorded on European beaches, regardless of the region. Consistently, top items include cigarette butts, plastic caps and lids. Crisp packets/sweet wrappers, cotton-bud sticks and plastic bags are highly frequent in the top items lists in Europe.
- In terms of the relative abundance of litter items, there are significant differences (but also variability) between regions and even within a smaller area.
- Recreational activities at/near the coast are a significant source of marine litter, in particular in the Mediterranean and Black Sea. Sea-based sources have relatively more expression in the NEA, in particular the North Sea.
- Packaging corresponds to a large fraction of litter items found on beaches. In study sites in the Black Sea coastline this can be as high as 70% of the litter items. Worth noting is that 44 to 90% of beach litter items are designed to be short-lived/single-use items.

5.3 Most common litter found on the seafloor

Litter is reported to be widely found on the seafloor in European seas (Table 5), including at all depths, from 35 to 4500 m (Pham et al., 2014). From a broad seafloor video survey made in the NEA and Mediterranean, Pham et al. (2014) reveal that sites nearer the shore tend to have higher litter concentrations, indicating proximity to land-based sources. Nevertheless, they also pointed out exceptions, which reflect the influence of other factors such as hydrography and geomorphology that affect litter distribution and accumulation. For example, the authors propose that high densities of litter found in submarine canyons

and low densities on the continental shelves may be explained by strong water flow from rivers that transports litter to deeper waters.

According to loakeimidis et al, 2017, the continental shelf of the world's seas has been extensively studied in what concerns the abundance and distribution of litter. Most of the data collected result from trawl surveys. Figure 8 illustrates densities of litter in the Mediterranean and other EU regional seas as reported by some of these studies.

Figure 8 - Seafloor marine litter densities in the Mediterranean and other European Seas. Source: loakeimidis et al. 2017.

Plastic is consistently reported as the dominant fraction of marine litter found on the seafloor. Pham et al. (2014) report that plastic items, other than derelict fishing gear, dominate in all the physiographic settings, including in submarine canyons, where litter seems to accumulate from coastal and land-based sources. Fishing gear, on the other hand, was the main type of litter found on

seamounts, banks and ocean ridges, reflecting the influence of fishing activity, which can be intense in these sites. In addition, the seafloor can harbour significant amounts of non-buoyant litter, such as glass and metal, which are hardly found in surface waters.

Fortibuoni et al. (2019) revealed differences in seafloor composition in different countries, likely reflecting policies over specific items (e.g. ban of non-degradable plastic bags in Italy but not in Croatia and Slovenia), as well as the influence of specific industrial activities, such as agriculture (plastic sheeting from greenhouses in Greece) and aquaculture (mussel nets from intensive mussel farming in Italy). In fact, the effect of policy implementation, in this case targeting single-use plastic bags, can explain the downward trends of bags found on the seafloor in the North and Celtic Seas, as suggested by Maes et al. (2018), while for the majority of other litter categories no statistically significant trends can be derived.

Table 5 - Top litter items recorded in seafloor surveys in European regional seas.

Regional Sea(s)	TOP items on seafloor	Reference
North East Atlantic, Mediterranean	Plastic bags Glass bottles Fishing lines and nets (34%)	Pham et al., 2014
Mediterranean (Adriatic and Ionian Seas)	Sheets, industrial packaging, plastic sheeting Plastic bags Plastic food containers Plastic bottles Mussel/Oyster nets Plastic cups and lids Other plastic items (identifiable) Synthetic rope Metal drink cans Sanitary towels/panty liners/backing strips	Fortibuoni et al., 2019
North East Atlantic (North and Celtic Seas)	Plastic bags Plastic sheeting Derelict fishing gear	Maes et al., 2018

KEY MESSAGES

- Litter in the seafloor tends to show higher concentrations nearer the shore, indicating proximity to land-based sources.
- Specific activities such as fishing, aquaculture and even agriculture can influence the composition of litter found on the seafloor.

6 Focus on North East Atlantic region

The North-East Atlantic (NEA) provides diverse marine environment and resources that supply a wide range of goods and services to millions of people in the OSPAR maritime area including food, transport, energy and amenities. Maritime economic sectors in the NEA are fisheries and aquaculture, shipping, ports, oil and gas industry, and offshore wind energy. These maritime activities can have consequences to the maritime ecosystem, thus OSPAR has been assessing the state of the marine environment and the pressures from human activities, such as the impact of marine litter to marine life ([OSPAR Quality Status Report, 2010](#)).

Marine litter has been monitored by OSPAR since 1998, starting from beach litter and subsequently expanded to offshore seafloor litter with the aim to reduce the amount of marine litter in the OSPAR area. The NEA beaches have an average of 712 litter items per 100 m and is still slightly increasing in input from the fishing industry. Limited data on seabed and floating litter are available but it has been found that the amounts of litter on the seabed can vary widely and that litter may accumulate in certain areas, even in the deep sea. An assessment of marine litter by OSPAR suggested the main sources of sea-bed litter are shipping and fishing, including abandoned and lost fishing gear ([OSPAR Quality Status Report, 2010](#)).

6.1 Reported amount of beach litter

OSPAR has been monitoring beach litter in the NEA since 1998 initially through a pilot project and then through a voluntary monitoring program. The trends in the levels of the amount of beach litter item from 1998 to 2008 are shown in Figure 9.

According to OSPAR (2017), the beach litter abundance and composition in the North East Atlantic (OSPAR Maritime Area) varies widely between sub-regions and even between beaches within the same sub-region. This illustrates the multiple factors affecting the input and distribution of litter on the marine and coastal environments. For the period of 2014-2015, the average total number of litter items per 100 m of coast were similar in the southern North Sea (311), Celtic Seas (434) and Bay of Biscay/Iberian (365) Coast but one order of magnitude higher in the northern North Sea (6090). The composition in terms of categories of litter items are presented in Figure 10 below. We

MAELSTROM

see that non-identified plastic fragments are the most abundant category in all sub-regions, resulting from the fragmentation of larger plastic items. Packaging items is the second most common, which mainly consists of plastic items including caps and lids, food containers, crisp/ sweet packets/lolly sticks and plastic bags. It is also clear that the relative proportion of nets and ropes (most likely from fishing activities) in relation to packaging items (most likely from consumer goods) is higher in the Arctic and North Seas than in the Celtic Seas, and Bay of Biscay and Iberian Coast. This may reflect a combined influence between the intensity of maritime activities, such as fishing, and improper littering/dumping activities or inadequate waste management in the different regions. Drink bottles and containers are the most recorded items. In the Iberian Coast and Bay of Biscay, cigarette butts, cotton bud sticks, and rubber balloons are the most frequently record items. Shotgun cartridges are most frequent in the southern North Sea, northern North Sea and Celtic Seas, which reflect hunting-related litter.

In summary, the OSPAR beach litter assessment has recorded the main marine litter types as plastic fragments, packaging, and nets and ropes. Some significant changes in the amount of litter recorded on survey sites in the period of 2009-2014, but no general trends across all survey sites were observed. The main source of litter was fisheries.

Figure 9 - Trends in the average number of items of marine litter collected on reference beaches in three-month periods in the OSPAR regions. Source: OSPAR Quality Status Report 2010.

Figure 10 - Composition of marine litter according to main litter types for the period 2014-2015 in the OSPAR Maritime Area. Source: OSPAR Intermediate Assessment, 2017.

6.2 Reported amount of seafloor litter

In the OSPAR assessment of composition and distribution of seafloor litter, widespread distribution of litter items was discovered on the seafloor of the Greater North Sea, the Celtic Sea, the Bay of Biscay, the Iberian Coast and the Gulf of Cadiz. The abundance of litter items on the seafloor increases from north to south of the NEA, and the majority of litter items are plastics. The number of plastic items collected by bottom trawls are most abundant in the Eastern Bay of Biscay (98%), Greater North Sea (68%) and in the Celtic Sea (58%) (Figure 11). The Eastern Bay of Biscay has the highest levels of recorded litter within the assessment area ([OSPAR Intermediate Assessment, 2017](#)).

The range of litter densities on the seafloor vary within the NEA region. Pham et al. (2014) found a density of 180/km² of plastic items in the seamounts, banks, mounds and ridges in the deep-sea of the Atlantic Ocean. Highest densities of litter were found close to coast and canyons in the Barents Sea (202 items/km²) and Norwegian Sea (279 items/km²) (Buhl-Mortensen and Buhl-Mortensen, 2017). Seafloor litter density of 6620 items km² was reported in the canyons near Lisbon using video footage and still images from ROVs (Mordecai et al., 2011). A long-term seafloor monitoring in the

MAELSTROM

Northwest Europe found a high variation in the abundance of litter items, ranging from 0 to 1835 pieces km⁻² of seafloor, whereas 63% of the 2461 trawls contained at least one plastic item. The most prevalent plastic litter items were bags, plastic sheeting, and derelict fishing gears (Maes et al., 2018). From a two-year survey of seafloor litter, the Baltic Sea seafloor litter abundance was significantly lower than in the North Sea (5.07 LI/km² vs 16.8 LI/km²), and plastic represented 80% of the litter items (Kammann et al., 2017).

A study of Gutow et al. (2018) on the floating and benthic marine litter in the southeastern North Sea found that bottom trawling was identified as a major source of marine litter. Floating litter was dominated by plastics (64%) such as plastic bottles, plastic bags and small plastic fragments. The next most common categories of floating litter were styrofoam, wood, and paper. Seafloor litter was found nearby river-mouths and nearby the coasts, which mainly composed of plastics. The most common plastic items on the seafloor were fibers from fishing nets, pieces of plastic foil, and other packaging material. Fishing-related items made up 76% of the total seafloor litter in the southeastern North Sea.

The distribution of seafloor litter in the southern North Sea is rather governed by near-bottom currents than by the source regime. Shear stress was the most influential variable in the distribution of seafloor litter and distance to major shipping routes was less important. Marine litter from the North Sea can be transported to the North Atlantic by currents or wind drag. Moreover, even litter items that are less vulnerable to wind drag such as plastic bags and foils can become deposited on the shore or transported by currents out of the North Sea into the North Atlantic (Gutow et al., 2018). Floating marine litter items in the southeastern North Sea is determined by the geographic location of the sources, and a large portion of the debris was also discharged from the rivers into the North Sea.

Figure 11 - Relative number of litter items per km² of the seafloor across the Greater North Sea, Celtic Seas and the Eastern Bay of Biscay, based on the number of items caught as by-catch in fisheries trawls. Source: OSPAR Intermediate Assessment, 2017.

KEY MESSAGES

- The NEA beaches have an average of 712 litter items per 100 m and is still slightly increasing in input from the fishing industry.
- Non-identified plastic fragments are the most abundant category in beaches in all sub-regions, resulting from the fragmentation of larger plastic items.
- Limited data on seabed and floating litter are available but it has been found that the amounts of litter on the seabed can vary widely.
- The distribution of seafloor litter in the southern North Sea is rather governed by near-bottom currents than by the source regime.

7 Focus on Mediterranean region

The Mediterranean Sea is a closed basin, with a coastal population of about 210 million inhabitants. Mediterranean countries are the number one tourist destination in the world, with around 360 million visitors every year, and receives waste from coastal zones, as well as from many large rivers flowing through largely urbanized cities such as the Nile River, which transports more than 200 tonnes of plastic into the Mediterranean Sea per year (Lebreton et al., 2017). In addition, more than 20% of global maritime traffic passes through the Mediterranean Sea. Consequently, the basin has become one of the most marine litter-affected areas in the world (UNEP/MAP, 2015).

Plastics are the prevailing type in all the matrices, accounting for up to 95-100% of total floating marine litter, due also to the high floatability of plastics, and more than 50% of seabed marine litter (UNEP/MAP and Plan Bleu 2020). The analysis of 80 beaches conducted in 2016 (Addamo, Laroche & Hanke, 2017) indicated that only 10 types of debris, mostly single-use plastics (cutlery/trays/straws, cigarette butts, caps/lids, plastic bottles, shopping bags) represent more than 60% of the total recorded marine litter on beaches. No change was observed in the percentage of the dominant marine litter categories between 2013 and 2018 on the beaches of 8 Mediterranean countries (Ocean Conservancy, 2018). Typically, most of the litter on beaches originates from beach/recreational activities. Glass bottles and metal beverage cans disappeared from the top ten lists in non-tourist areas in recent years because of behavioural changes.

The total plastic accumulated in the Mediterranean is estimated in the order of magnitude of 1,178,000 tonnes, with an uncertainty ranging from 53,500 to 3,546,700 tonnes (Boucher & Bilard, 2020) (Figure 12). Most of the plastic seems to be accumulated on the seafloor either as microplastics in the sediments or macroplastics scattered on the seafloor, with the rest being distributed in the other compartments.

Figure 12 - Plastic accumulated in the different compartments of the Mediterranean Sea. The three values for each box represent the low/central/high estimates. The central estimate is displayed as a full blue square and labelled with bold font. Values shown in metric tonnes. Seafloor plastic includes both the microplastics trapped in sediments and macroplastics deposited on the seafloor. Source: Boucher and Bilard 2020.

KEY MESSAGES

- The Mediterranean is one of the most marine litter-affected areas in the world
- Plastics are the prevailing type of marine litter, mostly accumulated on the seafloor
- The total plastic accumulated in the Mediterranean is estimated in the order of magnitude of 1,178,000 tonnes (with range between 53,500 and 3,546,700 tonnes)
- Proliferation of lighter marine litter items has been observed in the last decade (plastics, aluminium and smoking-related litter), as opposed to heavier items from basic use (bottles, cans) or marine litter originating from dumping activities (household appliances, construction materials, tires, etc.).

7.1 Most likely sources of marine litter

In most Mediterranean countries, the root causes of plastic pollution are found in the increase of plastic use, unsustainable consumption patterns, ineffective/inefficient waste management and loopholes in plastic waste management. Plastic ranges from 5% (Morocco), to 14% (Israel) of the total waste generated (UNEP/MAP and Plan Bleu, 2020). In some areas, up to 58% of the municipal solid waste collected is still disposed of in open dump sites. Of the millions of tonnes of plastic waste produced every year in Mediterranean countries, less than one third is recycled and plastics recycling is less than 6% (WWF, 2018). Another source of marine litter (macro-, micro- and nano-litter) is represented by untreated or poorly treated wastewaters. A key challenge is that in the Mediterranean region, 21% of wastewater (25% in Southern Countries) undergoes only basic treatment, and less than 8% of the total (1% in southern countries) undergoes tertiary treatment (UNEP/MAP 2017).

Key economic sectors in the Mediterranean, such as professional and recreational fisheries, aquaculture, tourism and shipping, also generate large amounts of litter that end up as marine litter (UNEP/MAP and Plan Bleu, 2020).

Items found on Mediterranean beaches indicate a predominance of land-based litter sources, stemming mostly from recreational/tourism activities (40% - 50% and more). Household-related waste, including sanitary waste, is also of great relevance (40%). The amount of litter originating from recreational/tourism activities greatly increases during and after the tourism season. Smoking related wastes in general also seems to be a significant problem in the Mediterranean (UNEP/MAP, 2015). With an evaluation of inputs from ships at 6 million tons worldwide and 30% of the maritime traffic worldwide occurring in the Mediterranean Sea, one may expect more than a million tons of garbage coming from ships to the Mediterranean (UNEP/MAP, 2015).

A recent survey conducted on some Mediterranean beaches showed that litter from shoreline sources, such as tourism and recreational activities and poor waste management practices, accounted for 38% (range: 14.4%-74%) of all litter collected; while the amount of litter from fisheries and aquaculture was at a level of 3% (range: 0.7-8.8%); sanitary and sewage related items accounted for 7%, while shipping, fly-tipping and medical related items accounted for 1% each (Vlachogianni et al., 2020).

Derelict fishing gear has been recognized as an issue of major concern in the Mediterranean (UNEP/MAP 2015). Fishing litter may be predominant in areas

MAELSTROM

characterized by intense fishing activities, such as the western Mediterranean Sea (Mordecai et al., 2011).

In the Tyrrhenian Sea the occurrence of marine litter was found mainly caused by fishing gear (Angiolillo et al., 2015), particularly lost lines, accounting for about 50% in the Italian regions of Campania and Sardinia and up to 80% in Sicily. The explored off-shore deep rocky banks in Sicily host numerous commercially relevant fishing stocks that attract local recreational and professional fishing boats, likely responsible for the great abundance of lines found in this area. Derelict fishing gears are found on the seabed in general, and in submarine canyons in particular. This was observed for example in the Sardinian continental margin (Central Western Mediterranean) at depths ranging from 100 to 480 m (Cau et al., 2017).

Also in the Strait of Sicily channel a Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) operated at depths ranging between 20 and 220 m, observed debris on the seafloor belonging to fishing gears: marine litter composition analysis allowed to identify demersal fishing, mainly represented by long-lines (LLS), as the most important activity carried out on the explored banks (Consoli et al., 2019).

In areas with intensive and extensive aquaculture activities mussel nets are among the most common items found. Findings from the DeFishGear project related surveys on beaches located along the coastline of the Adriatic and Ionian Seas show that mussel nets are the seventh most frequent item found (Mlachogianni et al., 2018). Furthermore, in surveys carried out along the Italian coastline, mussel and oyster nets were among the top three items recorded on beaches, while the results obtained from the seafloor surveys show that litter from aquaculture accounts for 15% of total items recorder (Pasquini et al., 2016). Indicatively some preliminary results from Fishing for Litter activities in the area show that mussel and oyster nets account for almost 30% of the total weight of the items collected.

Uncontrolled discharges also act as main sources of litter in the Mediterranean Sea. For example, approximately only one third of the 133 coastal cities in Algeria are controlling their waste discharges in adapted structures, without taking illegal deposits into account (Makhoukh, 2012). Furthermore, the percentages of inadequately managed waste in Mediterranean countries such as Albania, Algeria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Egypt, Lebanon, Libya, Montenegro, Morocco, Syria, Tunisia is estimated to range from 23% to 67%, with a mean of 48.8% (Jambeck et al., 2015; UNEP/MAP MEDPOL, 2015).

7.1.1 Pathways: watershed and rivers

The Top Items list in the Mediterranean Sea region (JRC, 2018) has been collated using data from 17 rivers and streams. The observers identified 3,486 litter items. The Top 10 items made up to 82.8% of the total number of items observed and included the following material categories: 7 plastic, 2 paper/cardboard and 1 metal. The Top 20 items comprised up to 96.3% of total items, including the following material categories: 10 plastic, 3 paper/cardboard, 2 processed/worked wood, 2 metal, 2 rubber and 1 cloth/textile (Figure 13). Plastic items in the Top 20 made up to 73.7% of total items. Plastic and polystyrene fragments reached 31.6% of the total items. The Top Item list for the Mediterranean is reported in Table 6.

Table 6 - Macro-litter in Mediterranean rivers: top 20 items list.

Ranking	Item	Material	MSFD Code	% of Total Items
1	Plastic pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm, > 50 cm	Plastic	G79 + G80	25.01%
2	Bottles	Plastic	G6	13.48%
3	Bags	Plastic	G2	9.87%
4	Cover / packaging	Plastic	G38	8.61%
5	Polystyrene pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm, > 50 cm	Plastic	G82 + G83	6.60%
6	Other paper items	Paper/Cardboard	G158	5.31%
7	Paper packaging	Paper/Cardboard	G149	4.93%
8	Cans (beverage)	Metal	G175	3.27%
9	Foam packaging/insulation/polyurethane	Plastic	G74	3.21%
10	Other plastic/polystyrene items (identifiable)	Plastic	G124	2.52%
11	Newspapers & magazines	Paper/Cardboard	G154	2.04%
12	Sheets, industrial packaging, plastic sheeting	Plastic	G67	1.81%
13	Crates and containers / baskets	Plastic	G18	1.78%
14	Other rubber pieces	Rubber	G134	1.61%
15	Other (metal)	Metal	G197	1.43%
16	Beams / Dunnage	Processed wood	G169	1.41%
17	Balls	Rubber	G126	1.00%
18	Wood boards	Processed wood	G168	0.89%
19	Fish boxes - expanded polystyrene	Plastic	G58	0.80%
20	Clothing (clothes, shoes)	Cloth/textile	G135	0.72%

Figure 13 - Mediterranean Sea – Macro-litter in rivers: top 10 items list.

Boucher and Bilard (2020) estimated the quantity of plastic (macro and micro) flowing every year into the Mediterranean. The estimated amount is 229,000 t/y (central estimate) with low and high estimates of 148,000 and 610,000 t/y respectively. The study considered the land-based sources only. The maritime ones were not considered.

The leakage is dominated by macroplastics, with only 6% stemming from microplastics in the central estimate (3% and 16% for the low and high estimates respectively) (Figure 14). The high mean mismanaged waste index in the Mediterranean basin (67%) explains the very high leakage from this source.

Figure 14 - Total annual macroplastic and microplastic leakage into the Mediterranean Sea using three estimates (low, medium and high). Source: Boucher and Bilard, 2020.

The Mediterranean countries contributing the most to the leakage are Egypt, Italy and Turkey, as a result of high quantities of mismanaged waste and/or large coastal

populations. These three countries may contribute over 50% of the total leakage, and the ten countries that contribute most are responsible for almost 90% of the total leakage in the Mediterranean basin (Figure 15).

Figure 15 - Leakage of macroplastic from mismanaged waste into the Mediterranean Sea, watershed view. For presentation purposes, the countries upstream of the Nile river are not shown. They are responsible for 9% of the total leakage. Source: Boucher and Bilard, 2020.

The annual macroplastic leakage from waste is estimated at a central value of 216,269 t/y (low value: 144,180 t/y, high value: 576,718 t/y). Each watershed contains in its vicinity dozens to hundreds of villages, towns or cities hosting different population densities, which, in turn, consume goods and generate waste. Surface water run-off (e.g. rain) greatly fluctuates between watersheds, entailing significant differences in the total macroplastic leakage between countries. The top three contributors to the overall leakage are: Egypt: 74,031 t/y; Italy: 34,309 t/y; Turkey: 23,966 t/y.

Cities and towns directly located in coastal areas (defined as areas < 23 km from the coast) are responsible for 35% of the total macroplastic leakage. The remaining 65% is generated further inland and carried by surface run-off directly towards the marine

MAELSTROM

environment. Surface run-off has been identified as a key contributor density high leakage, although not in all cases.

It appears that the watersheds hosting major rivers connected to the Mediterranean Sea present the highest leakage rates. The watersheds of the Nile, the Po and the Rhone rivers are responsible for macroplastic exports ranging from 900 t/y (Rhone) to 55,000 t/y (Nile). On a wider scale, it appears that all, watersheds export plastic debris into the marine environment in variable concentrations. In some cases, countries with a low population density present very high leakage rates per capita, i.e. emitted by each inhabitant of the country, possibly linked to waste mismanagement This can be seen for Bosnia and Herzegovina and Montenegro, with an annual leakage of 3 and 8 kg per inhabitant respectively.

Figure 16 - Leakage of macroplastic from mismanaged waste into the Mediterranean Sea, per locality view. Source: Boucher and Bilard, 2020.

When compared to the watershed mapping, it appears that some localities show high leakage even though they are not in a watershed or country that otherwise ranks high in the leakage assessment (Figure 16). This can be the case when a densely populated city is located within a watershed with relatively few inhabitants (e.g. Libya). The top 100 localities are responsible for 54% of the total macroplastic leakage, with 38% of them located in the coastal areas (Table 7).

MAELSTROM

Table 7 - The top 10 contributing localities and the total leakage into the Mediterranean Sea. Source: Boucher and Bilard, 2020.

Rank	Locality	Country	Income level	Leak _{waste} tonnes year ⁻¹
1	Muntazah	Egypt	UMC	1,912
2	Roma	Italy	HIC	1,809
3	Podgorica	Montenegro	UMC	1,662
4	Tirana	Albania	UMC	1,123
5	Skopje	North Macedonia	UMC	1,029
6	Waraq	Egypt	UMC	991
7	Umraniyya	Egypt	UMC	918
8	Tripoli	Libya	UMC	885
9	Kafr Al-Dawwar	Egypt	UMC	875
10	Al-Husayniya	Egypt	UMC	871

KEY MESSAGES

- Land-based sources are predominant, mostly from recreational/tourism activities and poor waste management practices
- More than a million tons of garbage can be expected to come from shipping
- Derelict fishing gear is as an issue of major concern particularly in areas characterized by intense fishing activities
- Aquaculture devices represent a source of litter in areas with intensive and extensive aquaculture activities (e.g. the Adriatic Sea)
- Plastics are the prevailing type of litter entering by rivers (about 70% of the Top 10 items)
- The amount of plastic (macro and micro) flowing every year into the Mediterranean has been estimated to be 229,000 t/y (with range between 148,000 and 610,000 t/y)
- Watersheds hosting major rivers connected to the Mediterranean Sea present the highest leakage rates: the watersheds of the Nile, the Po and the Rhone rivers are responsible for macro-plastic exports ranging from 900 t/y (Rhone) to 55,000 t/y (Nile)

MAELSTROM

7.2 Reported amount and type of litter found on the beach and on the sea-floor

7.2.1 Beach litter

The majority of studies performed to date in the Mediterranean have demonstrated densities in the 1 item/m² range but show a high variability depending on the use or characteristics of each beach. In fact, although useful data on types and quantity of marine litter exist in the region, they are inconsistent and geographically restricted mainly to parts of the North Mediterranean (UNEP/MAP, 2017).

By far the most predominant type of marine litter in the Mediterranean are cigarette filters (closely followed by cigar tips), which constitute a concern to the region and can be found even in the most remote coastal areas (Table 8).

Many studies on local beach surveys and marine litter collection provide information on the link between marine litter and tourism. During the summer season, the population of seaside towns sometimes doubles in comparison with wintertime. In some tourist areas, more than 75% of the annual waste production is generated during the summer season. According to statistics from holiday destinations in the Mediterranean (Bibione-Italy and Kos-Greece), tourists generate an average of 10% to 15% more waste than inhabitants. In the example of Kos Island, the tourism period lasts from April till October, with 70% of the total annual waste produced during this period (UNEP, 2011).

In a beach macro-litter survey (Mlachogianni et al., 2020) carried out in 23 sites located along the Mediterranean coastline, the vast majority of litter items (90%) were made out of artificial polymer materials, a category of litter dominant on beaches all over the world. The second most abundant group of litter items found were glass/ceramics (3%) (Figure 17). Items made of metal and paper accounted for 2% each, while rubber for 1%, processed wood for 1% and cloth/textile for 1%.

Similar results are available from the survey conducted in 56 sites in the Province of Alicante, in the Spanish south-eastern coast of Spain. Litter items were composed by different materials: plastic (82.6%), paper and cardboard (5.6%), pottery and ceramics (3.4%), metal (3.2%), cloth (2.3%), glass (1.5%), rubber (0.6%), wood (0.5%) and other unknown materials (0.3%) (Asensios-Montesinos, 2019). Litter diversity, expressed as the number of litter groups at each site, varied from 11 to 59 groups with an average of 26

groups per site. Other relevant information such as number of items per 100 m and number of items per m² at each site was also obtained (Figure 18).

Table 8 - Top fifteen beach litter items for the Mediterranean Sea and their share and average frequency per 100 m coast line (UNEP/MAP, 2017).

	Average # / 100m	Share
Cutlery/trays/straws (total)	131	17%
Cigarette butts	112	14%
Caps/lids (total)	110	14%
Drink bottles (total)	91	12%
Bags (e.g. shopping)	43	5%
Cotton bud sticks	37	5%
Bags	35	4%
Plastic/polystyrene pieces 2.5 cm >< 50 cm (total)	30	4%
Bottles	28	4%
Crisp/sweet packets and lolly sticks (total)	26	3%
Food incl. fast food containers	15	2%
Cigarette packets	12	2%
Cigarette lighters	11	1%
Drink cans	11	1%
Other sanitary items	9	1%
TOTAL	701	89%

Figure 17 - Characterization of beach litter from 23 sites along the Mediterranean coastline (Source: Vlachogianni et al., 2020).

Figure 18 - Characterization of beach litter from 56 sites along the western Mediterranean coast of Spain (Alicante province). Source: Asensio-Montesinos et al. 2019.

In Morocco, a total of 14 beaches, located between Tangier in the West and Saïdia at the East, were surveyed. Litter density varied from 0.154 to 0.001 items m^{-2} respectively for Marina Smir (in autumn) and Nador-Kariat Arekmane (in spring), the average value for all beaches being 0.06 ± 0.04 items m^{-2} (Driss et al., 2017) (Figure 19).

In terms of trends, observations have been made on the proliferation of lighter marine litter items in the Mediterranean (plastics, aluminium and smoking-related litter), as opposed to heavier items from basic use (bottles, cans) or marine litter originating from dumping activities (household appliances, construction materials, tires, etc.). This could be related to the efficiency of preventive actions (easier collection, recycling, adoption and/or implementation of stricter legislation with regards to dumping activities, etc.) for larger items and the difficulty to manage inputs from sources such as the general public (UNEP/MAP, 2017).

KEY MESSAGES

- Beach litter is generally dominated by single-use plastics
- Plastics are the prevailing type of marine litter, mostly accumulated on the seafloor
- Beach litter densities are generally in the 1 item/ m^2 range but show a high variability depending the use or characteristics of each beach
- The link between marine litter and tourism is well documented
- Cigarette filters are by far the most predominant type of beach litter
- Proliferation of lighter marine litter items has been observed in the last decade (plastics, aluminium and smoking-related litter), as opposed to heavier items from basic use (bottles, cans) or marine litter originating from dumping activities (household appliances, construction materials, tires, etc.).

Figure 19 - Composition of litter items (a) number of items and percentage of total collected items; (b) weight of items in kg and percentage of total weight of collected items from beach litter surveys on the Mediterranean Moroccan coastline (Source: Driss et al. 2017).

7.2.2 Seafloor litter

The Mediterranean Sea has been described as one of the areas most affected by marine litter in the world and plastic in particular, is highly impacted by hydrodynamics, geomorphology, and human factors. The Mediterranean geomorphology is very peculiar with not extensive shelves and deep-sea environments that can be also influenced by the presence of coastal canyons. Continental shelves are proven accumulation zones, but they often gather smaller concentrations of marine litter than canyons; as litter is washed offshore by currents associated with offshore winds and river plumes (UNEP/MAP, 2017).

In the Mediterranean, plastic which is the main marine litter component, is ubiquitous in the marine environment and may comprise up to 90% of the recorded seafloor marine litter (UNEP/MAP, 2017).

There are several studies investigating the abundance of marine litter on the Mediterranean seafloor (Galil et al. 1995; Galgani et al. 1996, 2000; Ioakeimidis et al. 2014; Pham et al. 2014; Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2013, Vlachogianni et al. 2017) but the information is still fragmented and geographically restricted to the northern Mediterranean. Most of the studies have been using traditional fish stock assessment methods i.e. otter trawlers, but recently new, costly and more sophisticated

MAELSTROM

techniques have been also used. Knowledge on the existence and importance of the corresponding accumulation areas in the Mediterranean still remain very limited (UNEP/MAP, 2017). In addition, modelling studies identifying hot-spots from sea-floor litter accumulation are available.

As reviewed by UNEP/MAP (2017), surveys conducted to date show considerable spatial variability on marine litter abundance. Accumulation rates vary widely and are influenced by many factors, such as the presence of large cities, shore use, hydrodynamics, and maritime activities. In the Mediterranean basin, some of the highest densities of marine litter stranded on the seafloor have been recorded, sometimes reaching over 100,000 items /km² (Galgani et al., 2000). Plastic densities on the deep-sea floor did not change between 1994 and 2009 in the Gulf of Lion (Galgani et al., 2011). Conversely, the abundance of litter in deep waters, such as the central Mediterranean, was found to increase over the years (Koutsodendris et al., 2008; Ioakeimidis et al., 2014).

Counts from 7 surveys and 295 samples in the Mediterranean Sea and Black Sea (2,500,000 km²) indicate an average density of 179 plastic items/ km² for all compartments, including shelves, slopes, canyons, and deep-sea plains. On the basis of this data, we can assume that approximately 0.5 billion litter items are currently lying on the Mediterranean Sea floor (UNEP/MAP, 2015).

Ioakeimidis et al. (2017) compiled several studies from the Mediterranean Sea, dedicated on the assessment and accumulation of seafloor marine litter with the use of otter-trawlers. Average number of items recorded in these studies have been collected and complemented with more recent ones. The resulting overview is provided in Table 9.

Today, much of the existing data on seafloor marine litter comes from trawl surveys conducted by commercial or experimental trawl fishery vessels, with numerous studies using this method. However, all these studies have been using different cod-end mesh sizes. Thus, the comparability of results remains to be clarified.

MAELSTROM

Table 9 - Litter abundance on the seafloor in the Mediterranean sea (items/km²), where not differently specified. Source: Updated from Ioakeimidis et al. (2017).

Western Mediterranean			
Gulf of Lions	1993-94	633-1935	Galgani et al., 1995
Gulf of Lions	1996	3900	Galgani et al., 1996
Gulf of Lions	1996-97	143	Galgani et al., 2000
Catalan Coast	2009	7003±6010	Ramirez-Llodra et al., 2013
Murcian Coast	2008-2012	4424±3743	Sanchez et al., 2013
Central Mediterranean			
Corsica	1993-94	633-1935	Galgani et al., 1995
Corsica	1998	229	Galgani et al., 2000
Ligurian Sea and Corsica	2011-2012	49.63 - 289.01	Erigny et al., 2019
Malta	2005	357	Misfud et al., 2013
Adriatic-Ionian			
		378	
Adriatic Sea	2011-2012	913 ± 80	Strafella et al., 2015
Adriatic Sea	2014	2300	Pasquini et al., 2016
Eastern Mediterranean			
Several areas		200-8,500	Galil et al. (1995)
Saronikos Gulf	2013-2014	1211±594	Galil et al., 1995
Saronikos Gulf	2013-2014	844±578	Ioakeimidis et al., 2015
Gulf of Patras	1997-98	240	Stefatos et al., 1999
Gulf of Patras	2000-2003	313	Koutsodendris et al., 2008
Gulf of Patras	2013-2014	641±579	Ioakeimidis et al., 2015
Gulf of Echinades	1997-98	89-240	Stefatos et al., 1999
Gulf of Echinades	2000-2003	641±579	Koutsodendris et al., 2008
Gulf of Corinth and Lakonikos Gulf	2000-2003	165	Koutsodendris et al., 2008
Antalya bay	2014-2015	13.3 and 651	Tunca Olguner et al., 2018
Mersin bay		0.01-5.85 kg/km ²	Eryasar et al., 2014

Regarding composition of marine litter, plastics have been shown to be ubiquitous in the marine environment, in vast quantities, and are present even on the most remote areas of the planet. This is evident in certain areas of the globe for which plastics can be found in excess, consisting more than 80% of the recorded marine litter items. Such areas (hot-spots) can also be found in the Mediterranean Sea (Table 10).

Table 10 - Plastic abundance (%) lying on the seafloor of the Mediterranean Sea. Source: UNEP/MAP (2017).

Study Area	Plastic (%)	Reference
Gulf of Lions (France)	64-77%	Galgani et al., 1995b; Galgani et al., 2000
Catalanian Provence (Spain)	60%	Sanchez et al.
Murcian Provence (Spain)	84%	Sanchez et al.
Central Med	87%	Sanchez et al., 2013
Corsica (France)	77%	Galgani et al., 1995
Maltese islands	47%	Misfud et al., 2013;
North-Central Adriatic Sea	24-62%	Strafella et al., 2015
Eastern Mediterranean Sea	36%	Galil et al. 1995
Gulf of Patras (Greece)	81%	Stefatos et al. 1999
Echinades Gulf (Greece)	56%	Koutsodendris et al. 2008
Gulf of Patras (Greece)	60%	Ioakeimidis et al. 2014
Echinades Gulf (Greece)	67%	Ioakeimidis et al. 2014
Antalya (Turkey)	81%	Güven et al., 2013
Mersin (Turkey)	73%	Eryasar et al., 2014
Limassol Gulf (Cyprus)	59%	Ioakeimidis et al. 2014
Saronikos Gulf (Greece)	95%	Ioakeimidis et al. 2014
Argolikos Gulf (Greece)	75%	Ioakeimidis et al., 2015

Estimates from modelling studies complete the picture of available knowledge. Spedicato et al. (2019) modelled distribution of marine litter on the seafloor and identified hotspots, particularly of plastic, through a spatial analysis at a northern Mediterranean scale, using generalized additive models (GAMs) applied to the data collected in 18 geographical sub-areas (GFCM GSA). A bubble plot of the plastic density indices by haul (items km⁻²) is presented in Figure 20, showing areas with higher plastic density in the Gulf of Lions (GSA 7), eastern Corsica (GSA 8), the eastern coasts of the Adriatic Sea (GSA 17 and GSA 18), the Argo-Saronic region of Greece (GSA 22) and southern Cyprus waters (GSA 25).

Figure 20 - Bubble plot of plastic data by haul from the MEDITS surveys of 2013, 2014 and 2015; for each haul an average value among the three years is shown (Source: Spedicato et al. 2019).

MAELSTROM

Figure 21 illustrates the map of the model predictions of plastic density in the northern Mediterranean basin, highlighting hotspots in terms of threshold densities corresponding to the 85th (149.1 items km⁻²), 90th (196.9 items km⁻²) and 95th (312.3 items km⁻²) percentiles.

Figure 21 - Map of the model predictions of plastic density on the seafloor in the northern Mediterranean basin. Density thresholds to identify hotspot areas are indicated in the legend in correspondence to the 85^o, 90^o and 95^o percentiles of the raster data. Source: Spedicato et al. (2019).

KEY MESSAGES

- Plastic may comprise up to 90% of the recorded seafloor marine litter
- Surveys conducted to date show considerable spatial variability on marine litter abundance. Accumulation rates vary widely and are influenced by many factors, such as the presence of large cities, shore use, hydrodynamics, and maritime activities.
- Cigarette filters are by far the most predominant type of beach litter
- Number of items/km² greatly vary in a range from dozen to thousands

8 The Adriatic Sea

The Adriatic Sea is an elongated basin which extends for about 800 km from NW to SE between Italy and the Balkan regions. The average depth of the Adriatic ranges from about 35 m (the northern part) to 140 m (central part), reaching 260 m in the Pomo Depressions. This semi-enclosed basin, surrounded by Italy, Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Albania, and Greece, receives freshwater mainly from the River Po (Gajšt et al., 2016), the largest Italian river, but is also fed by numerous other rivers that drain the highly densely inhabited, industrialized, and intensively cultivated areas of northern and central Italy (Sagratini et al., 2008). The Adriatic Sea collects a third of the freshwater flowing into the Mediterranean. The southern area of the basin lacks substantial riverine inputs (Mistri et al., 2017).

8.1 Sources of ML in the Adriatic

The Adriatic Sea subregion is characterised by the presence of many sources of marine litter, including large rivers, big coastal cities, touristic facilities, heavy shipping traffic, intense commercial fisheries and mussel farming (Liubartseva et al., 2016; Strafella et al., 2019). Many rivers form deltas along the northern coast, the most important being the Po river (Danovaro and Boero, 2019).

According to a recent study considering the entire Italian coastline, the Adriatic Sea is the most polluted subregion in terms of beach litter (590 items/100 m) (Fortibuoni et al., 2021). A high presence of aquaculture-related litter (mainly mussel nets) characterises the beaches in the Adriatic Sea (ibid). It has been estimated that 40% of marine litter enters the Adriatic basin through the rivers, an additional 40% through coastal urban populations, and the remaining 20% through shipping and fishing activities (Lebreton et al. (2012).

Van der Wall et al. (2015) focused on the small floating or suspended fraction of plastic litter - particularly small plastic particles (5 - 25 mm) and micro plastic particles (300 μm - 5 mm) - transported by rivers to the sea. They estimated for the Po river discharges 120 tons of litter and 7 E+11 micro litter particles/year, corresponding to 120 t/year.

Vlachogianni et al. (2018) investigated the possible sources of beach litter found in 31 beaches surveyed in the Adriatic-Ionian region. Of the total litter items collected,

MAELSTROM

33.4% originated from shoreline sources, including poor waste management practices, tourism and recreational activities. Some 9.68% of litter items were sanitary and sewage-related, while 5.25% was generated by fisheries and aquaculture. A percentage of 1.23% of litter was attributed to fly-tipping, 1.06% to shipping, 1.01% to medical related activities and only 0.04% to agriculture.

At the national level (Figure 22), the highest percentage of items originating from shoreline sources was recorded in Bosnia and Herzegovina (82%), followed by Montenegro (73.7%). In Albania, the contribution of items from shoreline sources was 47.4%, in Greece 46.1% and in Slovenia 45.1%. The lowest contributions of items coming from shoreline sources were observed in Croatia and Italy, where they accounted for 28% and 25.5% of all collected items, respectively. Fisheries and aquaculture related items had a substantial contribution in Italy (13.73%) and Greece (11.72%). The highest contributions of sanitary and sewage-related items were recorded in Croatia (12.33%) and Italy (9.57%), while in Albania shipping activities seemed to be responsible for a significant amount of litter (4.72%). The contribution of the remaining sources was low with fly-tipping and medical related items for all countries being in the range of 0.45-3.08% and 0.27%-1.11%, respectively.

Figure 22 - Figure x Sources of marine litter on the basis of aggregated results at the national level and at the Adriatic & Ionian level (Source: Vlachogianni et al. 2018).

The contribution of the sea-based sources (fisheries and aquaculture, shipping), the land-based sources (shoreline, tourism and recreational activities, agriculture, medical related) and mixed sources (sanitary and sewage related, fly-tipping, non-

MAELSTROM

sourced items) were also calculated (Figure 23). The highest contribution of sea-based sources vs land-based sources was observed for Italy (14.8% vs 27%) and Greece (13.2% vs 48.0%); while the lowest contribution was recorded for Montenegro (1.5% vs 74.1%) and Bosnia and Herzegovina (1.9% vs 82.8%).

Figure 23 - Percentages of items belonging to three different sources categories: land-based, sea-based and mixed (Source: Vlachogianni et al. 2018).

Vlachogianni et al. (2018) also calculated the percentage (%) of marine litter inputs from the fisheries and aquaculture sector for each survey site. The lowest marine litter contributions from the fisheries and aquaculture sectors were found for Montenegrin beaches, Kamenovo (0.6%) and Igalo (0.9%). The highest contributions were obtained for beaches in Greece and Italy. Specifically, the following percentages were calculated: for Arillas (Greece) 24%, for Foce Bevano (Italy) 20.3%, for Boccasette (Italy) 31.3%, for Mega Ammos (Greece) 37.5%. The main fisheries and aquaculture related items for Greece were polystyrene fish boxes and string and cord (among the top 20 items found), while for Italy the main items found were mussel nets and string and cord. Aggregated results at the national level show that the fishing related items contribution is highest for Italy (13.7%), followed by Greece (11.7%) and Slovenia (6.3%).

The relevance of fishery and aquaculture-related litter for the Italian coast of the Adriatic Sea is confirmed by the results of the surveys conducted at national level along all Italian coastline (Fortibuoni et al. 2021): in the Adriatic Sea, the densities of litter from aquaculture - consisting almost exclusively of mussel nets - were higher than in the Tyrrhenian and the Central Mediterranean, with a median density of 22

MAELSTROM

items/100 m. Mussel nets densities distribution was highly skewed, reaching extreme values (between 295 and 795 items/100 m) in four Adriatic beaches. These beaches have in common the proximity to mussel farms, and three of them are rural beaches without touristic facilities, and thus cleaning activities are not routinely performed, resulting in litter accumulation. In the last decades, the production of mussels has dramatically increased in the region and waste from mussel farms heavily pollutes the seafloor as well as the Adriatic beaches.

For the purpose of a modelling study to simulate the distribution of marine litter, Liubarseva et al. (2016) identified most relevant geographic sources of marine litter and provided an indirect estimation of their amount (Figure 24). Following Lebreton et al. (2012), they assumed that 40% of the marine litter enters the basin through rivers; 40% through coastal urban populations; and the remaining 20% is derived from shipping lanes. They yield 4000, 4000, and 2000 ton year⁻¹, respectively. Total river-born plastic input of 4000 ton year⁻¹ was distributed to be proportional to the average annual rivers' runoffs. Urban population data are taken from a database implemented by Brinkhoff (2010). The 46 largest cities located inside a 10 km coastal belt, which contained more than 20,000 inhabitants in 2010, were considered. Three cities situated on the north Ionian Sea coast are included due to their possible contribution to the floating debris flux through the Otranto Strait. Total coastal urban population input of 4000 t year⁻¹ was distributed to be proportional to the number of each city's inhabitants. To distribute the total plastic input of 2000 ton year⁻¹ along shipping lanes, 60 of the most congested lanes were selected. The intensities of the top 10 marine litter inputs into the Adriatic Sea were estimated and they are listed in Table 11.

Table 11 - Top 10 marine litter inputs into the Adriatic Basin estimated (Source: Liubarseva et al., 2016).

	Input	Intensity (ton year ⁻¹)	% of total inputs
1	Shipping lanes	2000	20.0
2	Po River	1349	13.5
3	Buna/Bojana River	575	5.8
4	Bari	351	3.5
5	Venice	291	2.9
6	Neretva River	283	2.8
7	Trieste	229	2.3
8	Split	198	2.0
9	Adige River	191	1.9
10	Ravenna	183	1.8
	Other rivers (58) and cities (41)	4350	43.5

Figure 24 - Spatial distribution of the floating debris inputs into the Adriatic Basin: shipping lanes (gray scatter plot); rivers (open blue diamonds), the largest rivers (closed blue circles); cities (open red circles); and the largest cities (closed red circles) (Source: Liubartseva et al., 2016).

8.2 Macrolitter on beaches and seafloor in the Adriatic

8.2.1 Beach litter

Vlachogianni et al. (2018) assessed 31 beaches (Figure 25) between 2014 and 2016, where in total 180 surveys were performed, and a total of 70,581 marine litter items were classified, recorded and removed. Items varied widely in abundance and types.

Aggregated results at national level (Figure 26) show that the abundance of litter on average is higher for the surveyed beaches in Croatia, with an average value of 2.9 items/m² (2914 items/100m stretch), followed by beaches in Slovenia with 0.50 items/m²

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(494.9 items/100m stretch) and beaches in Montenegro with 0.37 items/m² (374.2 items/100m stretch). For the beaches in Italy, Greece and Albania the following averages were calculated: 0.28 items/m² (280 items/100m stretch), 0.24 items/m² (201 items/100m stretch) and 0.22 items/m² (219 items/100m stretch), respectively. The lowest abundance of litter items was found on the beaches of Bosnia and Herzegovina, which are located in front of large-scale hotels and are cleaned up on a regular basis, with the average value of 0.17 items/m² (168 items/100m stretch).

Figure 25 Spatial distribution of beach litter densities for the 31 beaches (Source: Vlachogianni et al. 2018).

Figure 26 - Beach litter densities on an aggregated basis at the national level (Croatia is on the secondary y-axis). Whiskers indicate the interquartile ranges, the black dots denote the median values (Source Vlachogianni et al., 2018).

Marine litter items recorded were classified into 8 major groups of material types on an aggregated basis at the national and regional (Adriatic-Ionian) level. The majority of litter items were made out of artificial/anthropogenic polymer materials. In almost all countries of the Adriatic-Ionian region plastic items were in the range of 74–92% of total items recorded (with the exception of Albania, where plastics accounted for 54.3%), while at the regional level the amount of plastics reached 91%. The second most abundant group of litter items found in the region were glass/ceramics (3.2%), followed by items made of metal (1.5%), paper (1.4%) and cloth/textile (1.1%). Rubber items represented 0.6% of the total 70,581 items recorded in the region and only some 0.1% were classified as unidentified items and/or chemicals.

Plastic pieces larger than 2.5 cm and smaller than 50 cm in the longest dimension (G79) accounted for the highest percentage 19.89% (14,040 items) of the total litter items recorded in all surveys, followed by polystyrene pieces larger than 2.5 cm and smaller than 50 cm (G82) with 11.93% (Table 3). The third most abundant items were cotton bud sticks (G95) accounting for 9.17% of total items recorded, followed by plastic caps/lids from drinks (G21) with 6.67% and cigarette butts and filters (G27) with 6.60%. Plastic caps/lids unidentified (G23), mussel & oyster nets (G45), crisp packets/sweet wrappers (G30), glass or ceramic fragments 2.5 cm (G208) and other identifiable

plastic/polystyrene. Top-ten item lists are available also at the national level. Figure 27 reports the top-10 items of the Italian Adriatic beaches.

Figure 27 -. Top-ten items of the Italian Adriatic beaches (Source: Vlachogianni et al., 2018).

8.2.2 Seafloor litter

The abundance and composition of benthic litter in the Northern and Central Adriatic Sea were investigated at 67 stations with bottom trawl nets (Pasquini et al., 2016). Average density of benthic litter was 913 ± 80 items/km², ranking the Adriatic as one of the most polluted basins worldwide. Plastic was dominant in terms of numbers (80%) and weight (62%), and mainly consisted in bags, sheets and mussel nets. Higher quantities of litter were found in coastal areas, especially in front river mouths, coastal cities and mussel farms. In deep waters, litter hotspots were associated with most congested shipping lanes, indicating an additional litter input to the basin.

Benthic litter composition resulted to be largely driven by the vicinity to local sources, i.e. mussel farming installations and most congested shipping routes. The average densities of the six litter categories collected in the survey were: plastic 706 ± 72 items/km² (49 ± 25 kg/km²); glass 71 ± 18 items/km² (4 ± 1 kg/km²); other 56 ± 18 items/km² (14 ± 8 kg/km²); metal 29 ± 7 items/km² (9 ± 6 kg/km²); natural 25 ± 7 items/km² (4 ± 2 kg/km²); rubber 25 ± 5 items/km² (3 ± 1 kg/m²). Plastic appeared ubiquitous (Figure 28). Plastic litter hot-spots were located especially in front of the Po river estuary and touristic seaside cities. Metals and glass were more abundant in offshore stations (51–100 m depth), close to major shipping routes. Glass was abundant also in inshore stations (0–30 m depth) located in front of main Northern Italian harbours, Venice and Trieste. High densities of “other” material (clothes, shoes and other miscellaneous) were found up to 30 m depth in front of largest cities of the Northern coast, and between 51 and 100 m depth along the major shipping routes. Natural (mainly worked

or processed wood) was abundant along the Central coast, up to 30 m, while rubber (balloons, tyres, fishing bobbins, boots and gloves) represented a poorly represented category, heterogeneously distributed in the surveyed area (Pasquini et al., 2016).

Strafella et al (2019) too report on composition, density and spatial distribution of the marine litter collected on the sea-floor in the Adriatic sea during six survey years (2011–2016). These results are comparable with the ones from Pasquini et al. (2016). The mean density of total litter collected over six sampling years throughout the surveyed area (Figure 29) amounted to 102.66 ± 41.91 kg/km², while in the different years it ranged from 41.99 ± 9.16 kg/km² in 2016 to 162.50 ± 65.11 kg/km² in 2012. The lowest density (0.00 kg/km²) was recorded in 2011, 2012, and 2013, while the highest one was registered in 2012 (3802.23 kg/km²).

Figure 28 - Spatial distribution and composition of benthic litter. Spatial distribution of the total litter collected on the sea floor (A) and total marine litter composition in terms of numbers (B) and weight (C) (Source: Pasquini et al., 2016).

Figure 29 - Spatial distribution and weight of the total litter collected on the sea bottom (Source: Strafello et al., 2019).

The highest concentration of total litter was found in stations close to the coast within 30m depth with a mean weight of 142.90 ± 27.20 kg/km², while the lowest value was recorded between 30 and 50m depth (41.12 ± 9.62 kg/km²). Metal was the most abundant category within 30m depth (34.51 ± 15.39 kg/km²) followed, in the order, by other (30.04 ± 10.84 kg/km²), other plastic (OP) (28.54 ± 7.95 kg/km²), fishing nets (FN) (22.58 ± 7.91 kg/km²) and mussel culture debris (MCD) (11.57 ± 1.93 kg/km²).

Plastic was dominant accounting for 43% of the total litter collected during the sampling period, followed by metal and other litter representing, respectively, 24% and 20%. Glass, wood and rubber made up very small percentages (Figure 30).

Figure 30 - Seafloor litter composition in the Adriatic sea (Source: Stafella et al., 2019).

The above results are confirmed, in terms of composition of sea floor marine litter, by a recent survey conducted in the Adriatic-Ionian macroregion (Fortibuoni et al., 2019) where plastics were largely dominant (86.3%) and the large majority (77%) of litter items found during the surveys consisted of short-term & single-use objects (with slight differences in different countries, from 73% in Croatia to 86% in Montenegro). The top 10 most abundant sub-categories represented the large majority of litter found (82.5%). The sub-category “sheets, industrial packaging, plastic sheeting” was the most abundant (28.3%), followed by “bags” (14%), “food containers incl. fast food containers” (9%), “plastic bottles” (8%) and “mussel nets, oyster nets” (6%).

9 Marine Litter on the NW Portuguese Coast and Estuaries

Portugal is a coastal country located in the Europe South-Western region with 1230 km of Atlantic coast and an exclusive economic zone extending with 1,727,408 km², being part of Iberian Peninsula and having two archipelagos in the Atlantic: Madeira and Azores islands. Following the requirements of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), there has been an increasing effort on monitoring and research programs, reporting quantity, typology and effects of plastic marine litter and microplastics through Portuguese national agencies and research projects. However, there are still important gaps and restricted spatial distributions, with the majority of monitoring data and research studies being reported in the mainland centre and southern areas.

To date, the few scientific studies focused on the marine litter in the NW Portuguese Coast (Table 12) refer to floating marine litter (Sá et al., 2016; González-Fernández et al., 2018, 2021), benthic marine debris on the western Iberian continental margin (Neves et al., 2015), the occurrence of plastic marine debris in beaches (Martins and Sobral Antunes et al., 2013) and microplastics in the coastal waters, beaches and estuaries (Antunes et al., 2018; Rodrigues et al., 2019).

Table 12 - Summary of the studies across marine litter in NW Portuguese coastal area.

Area	Location	Matrix	Items	Reference
Continental shelf	Portuguese Coast	Seawater	Marine Litter (macro-floating marine debris (FMD))	Sá et al. (2016)
Coastline	Matosinhos	Sediments (bottom trawls)	Marine Litter	Neves et al. (2015)
Estuary	Ave	Water	Marine Litter	González-Fernández et al. (2018, 2021)
Estuary	Leça	Water	Marine Litter	González-Fernández et al. (2018, 2021)
Estuary	Douro	Water	Marine Litter	González-Fernández et al. (2018, 2021)
Coastline	Matosinhos	Sediments (beach)	Plastic debris	Antunes et al. (2013)
Coastline	Agudela	Sediments (beach)	Plastic debris	Martins and Sobral (2011)
Coastline	Matosinhos	Sediments (beach)	Microplastics	Antunes et al. (2018)
Estuary	Porto (Douro)	Water	Microplastics	Rodrigues et al. (2019)

As other coastal countries, Portugal is susceptible to the impacts of marine litter due to the extent and demographic pressures on coastal and estuarine areas, and also due to the activities around river margins. Litter pollution may originate from land or sea sources. The land-based sources are considered the main sources of marine litter in densely populated coastal areas (Andrady et al., 2011). Since water courses are the most frequent eco receptor for all groups (Vieira et al., 2007), this environment is more susceptible to litter contamination (Prata et al., 2020). However, sea-based sources of litter pollution can be also important and include touristic activities, commercial fishing, and shipping (Figure 31; Prata et al., 2020).

Figure 31 - Average concentration of macroplastics and microplastics on beaches, offshore seabed and seawater reported in continental Portugal classified in four classes of concentrations (source: Prata et al. 2020).

A study conducted by Sá et al. (2016) presented data on abundance and density of macro-floating marine debris (FMD), including their composition, spatial distribution and potential sources off continental Portugal (Figure 32). FMD were assessed by shipboard visual surveys covering the Portuguese Atlantic Coast. The surveyed sector, comprised between the northern border and Lisbon area presented the higher FMD diversity and abundances.

Figure 32 - Floating marine debris kernel density map. Kernel density estimates are presented in equal intervals of 10% increments, with warmer tones representing the higher concentration areas (10%). North sector and South sector (source: Sá et al. (2016)).

Another study conducted by Neves et al. (2015), in fishing trawls along the Portuguese continental shelf (depth range between 90-349m), revealed that plastic was the dominant litter fraction (76%) and was present in all trawls. In this work, the study area considered for the Portuguese NW coast included the Matosinhos region (41° 13' 43" °N, 9° 3' 6" °W), with an average of 100 litter items per km². A recent research work by González-Fernandez et al. (2021) provided information about floating litter entering the European Seas through river systems. This report included 3 estuarine areas from the NW Portuguese coast, namely Ave (41° 21' 4" °N, 8° 44' 22" W), Douro (41° 8' 23" °N, 8° 36' 33" °W) and Leça (41° 11' 45.2" °N, 8° 40' 57" °W). The mean litter flux reported was 9.97, 22.40 and 9.01 items per h, for the Ave, Douro and Leça estuaries, respectively.

Several recent citizen science projects have also contributed to the characterization of marine litter in the Portuguese NW coast beaches, including Cabedelo, Arda (Viana do Castelo), Estela /Barranha (Póvoa do Varzim) e São Félix da Marinha (Vila Nova de Gaia) (e.g. Portuguese Environment Agency (APA) - Marine Litter Monitoring Program on beaches - Quantification, composition of marine litter on 15 beaches in Portugal). The density of marine litter reported for Cabedelo and Estela beaches (the closest to the Portugal demo site), during 2017, was 0.48 items per m² and 0.01 items per m², respectively (<https://rmslapambiente.pt/>).

Another important data source for coastal marine litter is the EMODnet portal (<https://www.emodnet.eu>). The top 20 marine litter items collected and categorized for

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the Portuguese NW coast beaches, between 2010 and 2020, are compiled in the Table 13. These top 20 litter items represented 89.77% of the total collected, identified, categorized, and registered items for the Portuguese NW coast beaches. The non-identified plastic pieces between 0-50 cm represented approximately 47.59% of the total collected litter. The bottom trawled litter items, reported in the North-western coast of Portugal (data from 2010 to 2020; <https://www.emodnet.eu>) are compiled in the Table 14, and the plastic litter represented 68% of total collected items.

Table 13. The top 20 items list in the North Western Portuguese beaches compiled using data from 2010 to 2020 (<https://www.emodnet.eu>) and relative sources according to Table, 2 Annex 1)

Rank	Item	OSPAR Code	% of Total items	Source	Material
1	Plastic pieces 0 - 2,5 cm	1171	32.51	Non-Sourced	Plastic
2	Plastic pieces 2,5 cm > < 50 cm	461	15.08	Non-Sourced	Plastic
3	Caps/lids	15	6.38	Public litter	Plastic
4	Cotton bud sticks	981	5.96	Sewage-Related Debris	Mixed
5	Cigarette butts	64	4.86	Public litter	Plastic
6	Other plastic/polystyrene items	48	4.42	Non-Sourced	Plastic
7	String and cord (diameter less than 1 cm)	321	3.36	Fishing	Plastic
8	Foam sponge	45	3.28	Non-Sourced	Plastic
9	Crisp/sweet packets and lolly sticks	19	2.39	Public litter	Plastic
10	Drinks (bottles, containers and drums)	4	2.01	Public litter	Plastic
11	Floats/Buoys	37	1.92	Fishing	Plastic
12	Industrial packaging, plastic sheeting	40	1.17	Non-Sourced	Plastic
13	Sanitary towels/panty liners/backing strips	99	1.08	Sewage-Related Debris	Mixed
14	Cutlery/trays/straws	22	0.94	Public litter	Plastic
15	Small plastic bags	3	0.88	Public litter	Plastic
16	Rope (diameter more than 1 cm)	31	0.82	Fishing	Plastic
17	Bags (e.g. shopping)	2	0.72	Public litter	Plastic
18	4/6-pack yokes	1	0.68	Public litter	Plastic
19	Other wood < 50 cm	74	0.68	Public litter	Wood
20	Food containers incl. fast food containers	610	0.64	Public litter	Plastic

MAELSTROM

Table 14 - Sea bottom trawled litter in the North-western coast of Portugal (data from 2010 to 2020, <https://www.emodnet.eu>) and relative sources according to Table 2, Annex 1.

Rank	Item	OSPAR Code	Total Covered Area (km ²)	Items Density (km ² trawled)	Source	Material
1	Fishing nets	115/116	0.184	331.02	Fishing	Plastic
2	Other wood	74/75	0.047	126.47	Public litter	Wood
3	Bags	2	0.694	72.06	Public litter	Plastic
4	Fishing line (entangled)	35	0.348	66.13	Fishing	Plastic
5	Other plastic items	48	0.443	60.95	Non-sourced	Plastic
6	Rope (diameter more than 1 cm)	31	1.285	51.37	Fishing	Plastic
7	Other textiles	59	0.097	31.07	Non-Sourced	Cloth
8	Drinks (bottles, containers and drums)	4	0.098	30.48	Public litter	Plastic
9	Industrial packaging, plastic sheeting	40	0.374	29.41	Non-sourced	Plastic
10	Drink cans	78	0.143	27.89	Public litter	Metal
11	Clothing	54	0.255	27.48	Public litter	Cloth
12	Fishing line (monofilament)	35	0.558	21.52	Fishing	Plastic
13	Other		0.047	21.17	Non-sourced	Unspecified
14	Jars incl. fragments of jars	931	0.048	20.91	Public litter	Glass
15	Other rubber pieces	53	0.050	20.10	Non-sourced	Rubber
16	Bottles	91	0.105	19.05	Public litter	Glass
17	Other Metal pieces	89/90	0.106	18.83	Non-sourced	Metal

Considering the main possible sources for marine litter in the North Western beaches, according to the summed data reported in Table 13, the majority of beach litter items derives from non-definable sources, followed by public litter and sewage-related debris (Figure 33). As for seabed litter, 48% of the monitored items are related to fishing activities and 33% are related to public activities (Figure 34).

Figure 33 – Percentages of the different sources accounting for Top 20 items of beach litter.

Figure 34 – Percentages of the different sources accounting for litter items found on the seabed.

9.1 Plastics and Microplastics

The highest concentrations of plastics in Portuguese beaches were reported in the centre region, followed by Lisbon and the NW regions (Prata et al., 2020) (Figure 31 and 32). Martins and Sobral (2011) identified the main size classes in stranded plastic debris from several beaches sediment, including one from the NW coast area (Agudela). The

MAELSTROM

authors observed a total of 99 items per m² in this area according as described in Table 15.

Table 15 - Number of plastic debris recorded in beach sediments in the north coast of Portugal (Source: Martins and Sobral, 2011).

Plastic size class	<1 mm	[1-2] mm	[2-3] mm	[3-4] mm	[4-5] mm	[5-6] mm	[6-7] mm	[7-8] mm	[8-9] mm	[9-10] mm	[>10] mm	Total
N ^o of items	2	8	17	26	14	8	4	4	2	2	14	99

A study by Antunes et al. (2018) aimed to quantify microplastics (MPs) accumulation in beaches along the coast of Portugal, during autumn and spring (2011-2012). The urban Matosinhos beach was included in this research and presented an average accumulation of more than 300 items per m², including pellets, fragments, Styrofoam® and foam sponge, with different abundances between seasons (Table 16).

Table 16 - Abundance and diversity of microplastics recorded in the Matosinhos beach during autumn and spring between 2011 and 2012 (Source: Antunes et al, 2018).

Season	Pellets	Fragments	Styrofoam	Foam Sponge	Total MP
autumn	489 ± 393	205 ± 338	10 ± 33	2 ± 8	707 ± 544
spring	90 ± 98	33 ± 41	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	123 ± 114

The occurrence of stranded plastic marine debris along the Portuguese coastline was also investigated by Antunes et al. (2013). In this study, 98% of marine debris collected in the Matosinhos beach (41°10' 29" °N; 8 41' 28" °W - Portugal NW coast) were plastic (2397 items per m², 283 g per m²). The most representative class of plastic marine debris was the resin pellets, representing 53% of total marine debris items (1289 items per m², 30 g per m²). The collected resin pellets were dominated by white pellets (3618 items per m²), followed by aged pellets (543 items per m²), black pellets (514 items per m²) and coloured pellets (207 items per m²).

Concerning the water column, a study conducted by Rodrigues et al. (2019) investigated the contamination of an urban impacted estuary (Douro River estuary, NW Portugal) by MPs, including the abundance and distribution of MPs, as well as fish

MAELSTROM

larvae in this estuary. Different types of MPs were found, namely fibers, soft/hard plastic, colourful/transparent plastic, in a total of 2152 particles, with a mean density of 17.06 MPs per 100 m³. The overall number of MPs surpassed the number of fish larvae, with an average ratio of 1.0 fish larvae: 1.5 MPs. The temporal variation of the fish larvae: MPs ratio, showed that MPs were more abundant during most of the seasons, reaching a maximum of 1.0 fish larvae:4.4 MPs during winter period. During summer, fish larvae surpassed the density of MPs, with an average ratio of 1.0 fish larvae: 0.7 MPs (Rodrigues et al., 2019). In the same study, the highest concentration of MP was found in river stretches 7–9 km from the estuary, possibly due to the presence of a wastewater effluent discharge and a boat dock in this area.

9.2 Anthropogenic pressures in the Ave estuary (MAELSTROM Portuguese demonstration site, NW Portugal)

Located in the northwest of Portugal, the Ave River hydrological basin has an approximate area of 1390 km²; from its source in Serra da Cabreirato its mouth in Vila do Conde, its main river length is 101 km and its average flow at the mouth is 40 m³/s (Rocha et al., 2019). The Ave River estuarine area is located in the Vila do Conde municipality, in the district of Porto, with an area of 149.03 km² (data in 2013) with 79 739 (mean annual population change = 0.050%) inhabitants (data in 2019), subdivided into 21 parishes (<https://www.pordata.pt>). The municipality is limited to the north by the municipality of Póvoa de Varzim, to the east by Vila Nova de Famalicão and Trofa, to the south by Maia and by Matosinhos and to the west it has a coastline on the Atlantic Ocean (Figure 35).

The River Ave differs from other northern Portuguese rivers not only because of its high pollution levels but also because of the large spatial and temporal variability of pollutants concentration (Gonçalves and Alpuim, 2011; Rocha et al., 2019). During the last years, several monitoring works have been developed to assess the anthropogenic pollution in the Ave River and estuary, including emerging contaminants (e.g. Ribeiro et al., 2016; Caetano et al., 2016; Couto et al., 2018, 2019; Rocha et al., 2019).

Figure 35 - Location of Ave River basin and identification of potential litter sources.

Overall, the watercourses of the Ave hydrographic basin present serious disturbances, regarding physical and chemical, and biological levels, with few exceptions recorded only in the upstream area, close to the springs. These disturbances translate into several effects in the ecosystem, namely the degradation of the riparian curtain, the alteration of the channel, and the poor quality of the water, with significant consequences on the aquatic communities. The surrounding area of the estuary of the Ave river is characterized by a small wasteland with a few species of ruderal plants and very low fauna densities, focused on the left margin.

The information on the presence and categorization of marine litter is very limited. According to González-Fernández et al. (2021) the Ave River basin annual floating litter loading is approximately 87306 items (Table 17). This research represents the only work performed so far on floating macrolitter in the Ave River basin. Considering the other river basins located in the same region (NW coast of Portugal), the Leça and Douro presented estimated annual floating litter loading values of 78891 and 196258 items per year, respectively (González-Fernández et al., 2021).

MAELSTROM

Table 17 - Estimated Ave River basin macrolitter (FML) annual loading (Source: González-Fernández et al. (2021)).

Mismanaged Waste (tonnes y ⁻¹) in the whole basin	MEAN-based FML (items y ⁻¹)	MEDIAN-based FML (items y ⁻¹)
10408	87306	84942

Along the hydrographic basin of Ave river, several pressures are identified as being able to contribute to the occurrence of litter in the aquatic ecosystem. Agriculture is a significant source of debris in Ave river since around 31% of the hydrographic basin is covered by agriculture. This area is one of the most industrialized area of Portugal, supporting a huge number of industries, such as those of textiles (18 Installations covered by the IPPC regime - Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control) and surface treatment (electrolytic or chemical process; 11 with environmental license-IPPC) (Figure 3), metal plating, leather tanning, rubber and plastic, cutlery and metalworking manufactures (Rocha et al., 2019). These pressures resulting in high levels of pollution and decrease of water quality that have been registered in this region during the last decades (Couto et al., 2019). Other activities also contribute to the impact of marine litter in the aquatic ecosystem, such as landfills (5 plants: Urban solid waste and Non-hazardous industrial waste), aquaculture plants (5 installations), port facilities (4 ports in the transitional waters area), and tourism. The latter more pronounced in Ave estuary, due to the urban activities of the fishing town of Vila do Conde in the northern margin of the estuarine area.

MAELSTROM

10 The Venice demo site: analysis of available data on beach and seabed litter in the Venice lagoon and Venetian coastal area

10.1 Description of the study area

The North Adriatic Sea coastline is characterized by the presence of valuable ecosystems, which have been recognized as habitats that deserve protection. The Venice lagoon is a Special Protection Area (IT3250046, 79/409/CEE, DGP n. 441/2007) and it comprises two Sites of Community Importance (IT3250030 and IT3250031). Moreover, two rocky outcrops located in front of the towns of Chioggia and Caorle (within the metropolitan city of Venice), have been declared Site of Community Importance (SCI) in 2002 and 2004, respectively ("IT3250047 - Tegnue di Chioggia"; "IT3250048 - Tegnue di Porto Falconero"). Finally, Venice and its lagoon with over 120 small islands is property of UNESCO by abiding to all 6 criteria of Outstanding Universal value.

The entire area and its MPAs are impacted by marine litter in several ways (Pasquini et al., 2016; Liubartseva et al., 2016, Liubartseva et al., 2018). In particular, accumulation of marine litter on the bottom has been showed to be relevant (the western gulf of Venice was shown to be one of the most impacted area in the Adriatic Sea by Fortibuoni et al., 2019). The area is a top touristic destination in the world. The city of Venice received almost 13 million tourists in 2019. The beaches, especially those located north of the lagoon are among the most famous destination in Europe for beach tourism (Jesolo and Cavallino). In relation with this pressure, public litter is expected to be an issue in the area.

Fisheries is one main maritime activity and an important economic resource in the area. The fleet, according to the 2017 EU Fleet Register, was composed of 662 vessels provided with a range of fishing devices, both active and passive, such as bottom trawl, mid-water trawl, hydraulic dredges, gill and trammel nets, and traps (Veneto Agricoltura, 2017; Pranovi et al., 2015). The high productivity and richness in fishery resources makes the Northern Adriatic Sea the most exploited area of the Mediterranean Sea (Mazzoldi et al., 2014). The combination of an intense fishing activity and the characteristics of the sea bottom (presence of rocky outcrops) make this area exposed to the impact from ALDFG (Abandoned, Lost or otherwise Discarded Fishing Gear). The GHOST project (LIFE12/BIO/IT/000556; life-ghost.eu)

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showed accumulation of ALDFG in the rocky outcrops and its surroundings (Moschino et al., 2019). Moreover, the region hosts a number of mussel farms, accounting for nearly the 33% of the national production. Aquaculture, and specifically mussel farming, has been shown to contribute significantly to seafloor litter (Fortibuoni et al., 2019). High presence of mussel nets in the northern and central Adriatic Sea has been already detected by various studies (Strafella et al., 2015; Pasquini et al., 2016; Vlachogianni et al., 2018), even in protected areas (Melli et al., 2017).

The Gulf of Venice is also interested by intense maritime traffic from merchant ships, supplier vessels for offshore activities (e.g., gas extraction), ferries and recreational crafts. The Port of Venice is Italy's eighth largest port in traffic volume terms, and one of the most important in the Mediterranean for cruise ships, catering to an enormous flow of people and vehicles. Maritime traffic has been already recognized as a source for marine litter in the area (Liubartseva et al., 2018).

Finally, the area is influenced by input from rivers: river Livenza, river Piave and river Sile mouths, located north of the Venice lagoon, various minor rivers and canal inflowing in the lagoon, and river Brenta mouth located south of the lagoon and, more south, the river Po delta. Noticeably, main direction of marine currents in the area is north-south, parallel to the coast. The main sources of marine litter for the Northern Adriatic are shown in Figures 36 and 37.

Figure 36 - Map showing some of the main land-based sources of marine litter (i.e. rivers, cities and touristic beaches) and aquaculture farms (i.e. mussel farm) for the area of the Northern Adriatic.

Figure 37 - Maps showing the density of maritime traffic in the northern Adriatic related to cargos, passenger ships and fishing vessels.

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10.2 Beach litter

10.2.1 Methodologies

Results from beach litter monitoring performed in the past years, i.e. from 2015 to 2021, were collected in a database. The sources of the data were EMODNET database and monitoring activities organised by various NGOs. The protocols of the various surveys were comparable, so the data were analysed as a unique database. The location of the surveys are reported in Figure 38 and Table 18, which reports the identification number and the coordinates of each sampling site and the date of each survey in the various sampling sites.

Figure 38 - Beaches monitored over time for marine litter along the Venetian coastline.

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Table 18 - Beaches monitored along the Venetian coastline: location, sampling dates and data source.

Site	Latitude	Longitude	Sampling Date	Sample Name	Data Source
Brussa	45.621847	12.958228	2015-10-20	BR10/15	EMODNET
			2015-10-22	BR10/15	EMODNET
			2016-03-29	BR03/16	EMODNET
			2016-03-31	BR03/16	EMODNET
			2016-10-19	BR10/16	EMODNET
			2016-10-31	BR10/16	EMODNET
			2017-02-15	BR02/17	EMODNET
			2017-10-09	BR10/17	EMODNET
			2018-03-26	BR03/18	EMODNET
			2018-10-17	BR10/18	EMODNET
Cavallino	45.477728	12.57639	2017-02-16	CV02/17	EMODNET
			2017-02-20	CV02/17	EMODNET
			2017-10-06	CV10/17	EMODNET
			2018-03-20	CV03/18	EMODNET
			2018-04-24	CV04/18	EMODNET
			2018-10-10	CV10/18	EMODNET
Lazzaretto	45.456000	12.388593	2021-04-24	LZ04/21	NGO ¹
Lido, Hospital	45.421388	12.363055	2019-03-16	L-H 03/19	NGO ²
			2019-12-06	L-H 12/19	NGO ²
			2020-02-13	L-H02/20	NGO ²
Lido, S. Nicolò	45.425114	12.392967	2019-03-16	L-SN03/19	NGO ²
			2019-12-06	L-SN12/19	NGO ²
			2020-02-13	L-SN02/20	NGO ²
Pellestrina	45.279312	12.303870	2019-12-12	PL12/19	NGO ²

¹ Venice Lagoon Plastic Free

² Legambiente Venezia

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Chioggia	45.199032	12.303777	2015-10-20	CH10/15	EMODNET
			2016-03-29	CH03/16	EMODNET
			2016-10-19	CH10/16	EMODNET
			2017-02-15	CH02/17	EMODNET
			2017-02-20	CH02/17	EMODNET
			2017-10-09	CH10/17	EMODNET
			2017-10-12	CH10/17	EMODNET
			2018-03-26	CH03/18	EMODNET
			2018-10-17	CH10/18	EMODNET
Barricate	44.841787	12.457776	2019-03-14	BA03/19	EMODNET
			2019-03-26	BA03/19	EMODNET
			2019-10-22	BA10/19	EMODNET
			2019-10-23	BA10/19	EMODNET
			2019-10-31	BA10/19	EMODNET

The data on number of items per 100 m collected from the NGOs and from the EMODNET database are classified using different categories: the NGOs data are classified according to the G categories used at European level (MSFD Technical Steering Group Marine Litter - General code, whereas the EMODNET data are classified according to a national classification used for MSFD monitoring programs in Italy: IT categories). With the aim to make all the available data comparable, a conversion was performed from G categories (the most specific) to IT categories (the most general), according to Table 1 of the Annex 1.

When more than one survey was performed in the same site, mean \pm s.d. of beach litter were calculated to have an average value for the beach.

The top 10 list of most frequent items recorded in the Venice lagoon and in the Veneto coastal area was determined summing up the number of items recorded for each IT categories in all sampling sites and surveys.

To each IT category, a specific source was then associated, according to the correspondence indicated in Table 2 of the Annex 1. The source is defined as the

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economic sector or human activity from which litter originates (Veiga et al., 2016). The association of each category to a specific source allows to define the main sources for the study area. In Table 3 of the Annex 1, the relations between IT and G categories, their possible sources and materials are reported.

Lastly, a multivariate analysis, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), was performed on a data matrix including the top 10 of IT categories and the monitored beaches in the different sampling surveys, to relate their spatial distribution with the various items. A second PCA was carried out relating sites with the sources of item categories. PCAs were performed using STATISTICA 7.0 software package.

10.2.2 Results and Discussion

The total number of items found in each beach at each sampling period were reported in Tables 4 a-e of the Annex 1. The total number of items found ranged from 3336 items / 100 m to 40 items / 100 m. The beach with the higher number of litter items was Cavallino in the survey of 2018-03-20 (3336 items / 100 m), followed by Barricata in the survey of 2019-03-26 (2025 items / 100 m) and Cavallino in the survey of 2018-10-10 (2016 items / 100 m).

Table 19 and Figure 39 report the mean values calculated for each site considering the different sampling periods. The beach showing the highest mean value of litter items is Cavallino (influenced by intense bathing tourism, downstream of the Livenza and Piave river mouth and in the vicinity of one of the Venice lagoon inlets), followed by Lido – S. Nicolò and the island of Lazzaretto (here only a sampling survey was performed). The latter two sites are strongly influenced by the urban site of Venice, whereas Cavallino is a touristic destination particularly in the summer period (beach tourism), with high number of camping sites. The highest number of items were found in March, before the cleaning operations of the beaches, generally performed before the touristic season.

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Table 19 - Mean values, maximum and minimum values, standard deviations and cv for each sampling sites.

Beach	Mean	Max	Min	Stand. Dev.	CV
<i>Lido, Hospital</i>	638	926	429	258	0,40
<i>Lido, S. Nicolò</i>	1068	1229	953	144	0,13
<i>Pellestrina</i>	213	213	213	0	0,00
<i>Lazzaretto</i>	1022	1022	1022	0	0,00
<i>Brussa</i>	612	1833	90	478	0,78
<i>Cavallino</i>	1434	3336	336	1124	0,78
<i>Chioggia - Sottomarina</i>	343	719	40	267	0,78
<i>Barricate</i>	836	2025	262	759	0,91

Figure 39 - Mean values of items found in the monitored beaches.

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Table 20 - Top ten of the IT categories showing the highest number of items considering all the sampling sites and periods.

	IT category	Total N. of items	Description
1	IT19	6464	Other plastic items and fragments
2	IT7	5983	Cups and cup lids / Cutlery and trays / Straws and stirrers Plastic rings from bottle caps / lids / Crisps packets/sweets wrappers / Plastic caps/lids chemicals, detergents / Plastic caps/lids unidentified / Drink bottles / 4/6-pack yokes, six-pack rings / Plastic caps/lids drinks / Food containers incl. fast food containers
3	IT32	3755	Cigarette butts
4	IT17	2406	Crab and lobster pots and tops / Tags / Octopus pots / Mussels nets, Oyster nets / Oyster trays (round from oyster cultures) / Plastic sheeting from mussel culture
5	IT18	1663	Other polystyrene items
6	IT53	1342	Cotton bud sticks
7	IT1	1032	Bags, shopping bags, garbage bags / small plastic bags, e.g. freezer bags / Plastic bag ends from pull off plastic bags / fragments of plastic sheets
8	IT50	923	Construction material (brick, cement, pipes)
9	IT51	835	Glass or ceramic fragments / Other glass items
10	IT12	545	Foam sponge / Fertiliser and animal feed bags / Mesh vegetable bags / Sheets, industrial packaging, plastic sheeting / Fibre glass and fragments / Hard hats/Helmets

The most frequent IT category, i.e. IT19, was that of plastic pieces and fragments of different sizes, followed by the category of food-related items and then cigarette butts (public litter related to intense tourism activity and proximity of river mouths). Interestingly, aquaculture and fishing-related items are at fourth place, as expected due to the intensity of these activities in the area. In particular, mussel nets (socks), deriving from mussel farming activities, were particularly abundant.

The top 10 items are very much in accordance with those found at the Italia Adriatic level by Vlachogianni et al. (2018), with the exception of the 7th item category IT1 (Bags, shopping bags, etc.) and the 9th item category IT51 (glass or ceramic fragments / Other glass items) which are characteristic of the beaches of the study area (Table 20).

Figure 40 shows the relative abundance of each IT category of the top ten list in each beach. Brussa is mainly characterised by the presence of cigarette butts, whereas Barricate by plastic pieces and fragments.

Figure 40 - Relative abundance of each of the top ten categories in some monitored beaches.

The PCA performed considering the dataset based on the 10 most frequent IT categories found in the monitored beaches in the different sampling surveys (Figure 41) shows that some sites are spatially separated due to the effect of the specific IT categories. The beaches of Lido and in its vicinity are characterised by the presence of more than 100 items / 100 m belonging to IT 51 (Glass or ceramic fragments / Other glass items), differently to all other beaches where this category is generally absent. While glass fragments can be related with recreational activities taking place in the area, ceramic fragments are indicators of inappropriate disposal of construction-related wastes which is known to be a common practice in the area. The spatial distribution of sites confirms that Cavallino is the most impacted beach for litter presence, not only deriving from public activities (domestic and touristic waste), but also from fishery (i.e. IT 12 and IT19).

Figure 41 - PCA performed with a data set including the top ten of IT categories found in the monitored beaches. Factor 1 showed significant positive loadings of the variables IT 7,12, 18, 19 and 53; Factor 2 showed significant positive loading of the variable IT51.

The main source for beach litter calculated on the whole dataset is related to public activities (domestic and touristic waste), the second category is represented by litter waste whose source is not identifiable and then fishing-related litter (Figure 42).

Figure 42 - Relative abundances of each litter source calculated on the whole dataset and n. of items found for each source.

Figure 43 - Abundances of items according to their sources in each monitored beach over time.

Considering the abundances of items according to their sources in each monitored beach over time, fishing-related items are particularly frequent in 2 surveys performed at Cavallino beach and in 1 survey performed at Lido – S. Nicolò. These beaches are located in the vicinity of mussel-farm areas. Moreover, irregular disposal of fishing nets at sea are known to be practiced in a marine area located in front of the Cavallino beach, i.e. the outcrop “Cavallino vicino” (Moschino et al., 2019). Other than that, the category “sewage related-waste”, composed by sanitary items such as condoms, nappies, cotton bud sticks etc, is particularly abundant in the beaches of Cavallino, Chioggia – Sottomarina and Barricata. These beaches are influenced by river mouths (Livenza and Piave in the case of Cavallino), by the city of Venice, not having a real sewage system and the mouth of river Brenta (in the case of Chioggia – Sottomarina) and the delta of Po river in the case the beach of Barricata (Figure 43).

Plastic represents the main material that composes the items found in beach litter calculated on the whole dataset (Figure 44), accounting for the 70% of overall items. The second most frequent material is paper, followed by Glass / ceramic.

Figure 44 - Relative abundances of each material composing the litter items calculated on the whole dataset and n. of items found for each material.

10.3 Seabed litter

10.3.1 Methodologies

The seabed dataset is derived by EMODNET and is composed of 32 stations. The localization of the stations is shown in Figure 45 and corresponds to 4 surveys, each one composed by 8 stations. The identification number of each station for each survey is reported in Figure 46.

Figure 45 - Localization of the 32 stations monitored for the presence of seabed litter.

Figure 46 - Detailed information for each of the 4 surveys performed to monitor seabed litter.

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In our analysis we considered the whole dataset, without distinguishing the temporal variability, representing the ML seabed state in the area. Moreover, as all the data used in this analysis derived from the same database, differently from what was done for the beach litter, the G categories originally used for the classification of litter items were maintained. More information on G categories are available in Galgani et al., 2020. All the data are expressed by n. of items / haul. The top 10 list of most frequent items was calculated summing up the number of items recorded for each G category found in all the monitored station.

As for beach litter, a specific source was associated to each G category according to the Table 1 of the Annex 2. The source is defined as the economic sector or human activity from which litter originates according to Veiga et al., 2016 (see Table 1 Annex 2).

Lastly, a multivariate analysis, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), was performed on a data matrix including the top 10 list of G categories and the monitored stations to relate their spatial distribution with the various items. PCAs were performed using STATISTICA 7.0 software package.

10.3.2 Results and Discussion

The total amount of items found in the seabed accounted for 1116 items (as sum of the items found in the 32 stations). The sum of the number of items observed in each station is shown in Figure 47. The number of items per G categories found in each station and the overall number of items per station is reported in Tables 2a-d of the Annex 2.

The highest abundance of items was located near to the coast and in the southern part of the area, downstream Chioggia inlet; this area corresponds to stations 2, 5, 8, 26, 27, 31. In particular, the stations 2, 8 and 31 were the most impacted by the presence of seabed litter, with 123, 118 and 111 items / haul, respectively. Considering the whole database, the most represented categories are reported in Figure 48. Abundances were obtained by the sum of the number of items found for each category in the 32 stations. Table 21 shows the top 10 list of most frequent items recorded in the seabed according to G categories. The G categories that show the greatest number of items are G67, i.e. sheets, industrial packaging, plastic sheeting, G10, i.e. food containers and G45 mussel nets

Figure 47 - Total amount of marine litter items monitored in each station.

Figure 48 - Most represented G categories.

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Table 21 - Top ten list of the G categories showing the highest number of items considering all the sampling stations.

	G category	Total N. of items / haul	Description	Source
1	G67	284	Sheets, industrial packaging, plastic sheeting	Public litter
2	G10	227	Food containers incl. fast food containers	Public litter
3	G45	195	Mussels nets, Oyster nets	Fishing
4	G2	89	Bags	Public litter
5	G79	53	Plastic pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm	Non-Sourced
6	G96	51	Sanitary towels/panty liners/backing strips	Sewage-Related Debris
7	G6	45	Bottles	Public litter
8	G124	24	Other plastic/polystyrene items (identifiable)	Non-Sourced
9	G134	22	Other rubber pieces	Non-Sourced
10	G51	14	Fishing net	Fishing

Generally, the most frequent typologies of items found in the seabed are similar to those found in the beach survey (i.e. plastic sheets for packaging, food containers, mussel nets and fishing nets etc.). The only item that appeared exclusively as seabed litter is represented by rubber pieces, typically a heavy material that easily sinks, probably deriving by tyres and belts.

The main source for seabed litter calculated on the whole dataset is represented by public activities (domestic and touristic waste), similarly to what observed for beach litter. The second category, however, is represented by litter whose source is related to shipping activities and the third to fishing-related activities (Figure 49 and 50). The northern Adriatic Sea is subject to heavy marine traffic from merchant ships, supplier

vessels for offshore activities (e.g., gas extraction), ferries, and recreational crafts. The greater amount of shipping related litter found in the seabed with respect to beach litter suggests a direct release at sea of this waste from ships and vessels.

Figure 49 - Relative abundances of each litter source calculated on the whole dataset and n. of items found for each source.

Figure 50 - Abundances of items according to their sources in each monitored station.

Moreover, fishing represents an important economic resource for the Veneto Region (North Adriatic, Italy). The high productivity and richness in fishery resources makes the Northern Adriatic Sea the most exploited area of the Mediterranean Sea (Mazzoldi et al., 2014). In particular, the port of Chioggia, located in the southern part of the Venice Lagoon, hosts the most important fishing fleet in the basin, with a total

of 213 active fishing boats in 2016, according to the EU Fleet Register. Interestingly, the higher amount of fishing-related litter was found in the stations 8 and 31, located in front of Chioggia, suggesting that this areas could be used by fishermen as an illegal dumping area during the return to port (Moschino et al., 2019; Melli et al., 2017).

These observations were also confirmed by the spatial distribution of the stations highlighted by the PCA (Figure 51). In particular, the analysis spatially separated the stations 8 and 31 mainly according to the fishing-related categories (G45 and G51), for the reasons previously discussed, and the stations 2 and 26. The G categories mainly associated to their spatial separation are related to public and non-sourced litter. The stations 2 and 26, located just in front of the Po delta, are affected by the inputs from the river. The Po is the country's largest river with a length of 673 km and a drainage basin of 71,000 km². It flows through one of the most productive agricultural and industrial areas in the country, entering the northern Adriatic Sea through a large delta with five distributaries.

Figure 51- PCA performed with a matrix made of a data set including the top 10 of G categories found in the monitored stations. Factor 1 showed significant negative loadings of the variables G10, G124, G2, G6, G67 and G79; Factor 2 significant positive loadings of the variables G134, G45 and G51.

MAELSTROM

11 Conclusions

The main aims of this review were to improve the understanding of the amounts and types of ML occurring in Europe and in particular in the study areas, to improve the understanding of the main sources and pathways of ML and to support the definition of the input data and assumptions related to M,L to be used in numerical models of ML spatial distribution in the Task 2.2.

In Europe, some differences were highlighted at regional level regarding ML input from rivers, with plastic packaging associated to consumers showing relatively higher presence in Mediterranean rivers than industrial and transport associated items. Moreover, floating litter fluxes analysed in European rivers show a broad variation across rivers but also within individual rivers, fluxes often varying between two or three orders of magnitude. Lastly, small coastal basins seem to discharge most of the riverine litter items exported into the seas. Countries with long and highly populated coastal areas are among the largest contributors of riverine litter loads in Europe. According to the analyses of beach litter, recreational activities at coast are a significant source of marine litter, in particular in the Mediterranean and Black Sea. Sea-based sources have relatively more expression in the NEA, in particular the North Sea.

Comparing the two regional seas we mainly focused on, i.e the North East Atlantic and the Mediterranean Basin, the differences in data availability has to be highlighted. The Mediterranean basin has been widely studied, whereas more limited information is available for the NEA, in particular on seabed and floating litter amount and distribution.

As regards the OSPAR monitoring data on beach litter, plastic fragments, packaging, and nets and ropes are the most abundant categories considering the NEA regions. For the period of 2014-2015, the average total number of litter items per 100 m of coast were similar in the southern North Sea (311), Celtic Seas (434) and Bay of Biscay/Iberian (365) Coast but one order of magnitude higher in the northern North Sea (6090).

In the OSPAR assessment of composition and distribution of seafloor litter, widespread distribution of litter items was discovered on the seafloor of the Greater North Sea, the Celtic Sea, the Bay of Biscay, the Iberian Coast and the Gulf of Cadiz. The abundance of litter items on the seafloor increases from north to south of the NEA, and the majority of litter items are plastics.

MAELSTROM

Considering the data available for the NW Portuguese Coast and the Ave Estuary, the majority of beach litter items derives from non-definable sources (56%), followed by public litter (20%) and sewage-related debris (7%). As for seabed litter, 48% of the monitored items are related to fishing activities and 33% are related to public activities.

The high percentages of non-sourced items found in the beaches is mainly due to pieces and fragments derived from the breakdown of the items, suggesting that extreme marine weather conditions typical of oceanic regions probably favour the fragmentation of plastic items. Large plastic items undergo fragmentation processes mainly as a consequence of mechanical breakdown caused by physical phenomena such as the abrasion with the seafloor and due to wave action. Consequently, it is also conceivable that part of this fragments and pieces were brought back to the beaches from the sea during storm events. The high number of items related to fishing activities found in the seabed were probably accountable to voluntary abandonment or accidental loss due to adverse meteorological conditions during fishing activities.

The Ave river demo site represents a case of a relatively small river going through regions characterized by high human pressures. Their distribution is not homogeneous along the river and this differentiates the ML distribution and transport. Potentially, this river represents a source of large amount of ML for the sea and it is particularly relevant to assess its relevance, considering the recent consideration on the role of small rivers in global ML pollution (Meijer et al., 2021).

The Mediterranean is one of the most marine litter-affected areas in the world. Land-based sources are predominant, mostly from recreational/tourism activities and poor waste management practices. Derelict fishing gear is as an issue of major concern particularly in areas characterized by intense fishing activities. In some areas, like the Adriatic Sea, aquaculture devices represent a major source for litter. Watersheds hosting major rivers connected to the Mediterranean Sea present the highest ML leakage rates: the watersheds of the Nile, the Po and the Rhone rivers are responsible for macro-plastic exports ranging from 900 t/y (Rhone) to 55,000 t/y (Nile).

The Adriatic Sea is the most polluted Italian sub-region in terms of beach litter. A high presence of aquaculture-related litter (mainly mussel nets) characterises the beaches in area. It has been estimated that 40% of ML enters the Adriatic basin through the

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rivers, an additional 40% through coastal urban populations, and the remaining 20% through shipping and fishing activities.

In the Venice demo-site a variety of human activities takes place, all representing sources for ML. In addition, the area is exposed to pathways of ML contamination. In fact, the area is characterized by the presence of river mouths, coastal cities (including Venice, top world-wide touristic destination), touristic beaches, intense mussel farming activities, fishing, shipping traffic. This variety of sources makes the identification of specific sources for beach and seabed litter particularly challenging. Public litter represents the first source of ML items found on the beaches of the area while non-sourced litter is the second ranked source, followed by aquaculture and fishing. In particular, mussel nets (socks), deriving from mussel farming activities, are particularly abundant, due to the intensity of these activities in the area. Differently from beach litter one, the seafloor litter distribution (total number of items) shows a clear geographic pattern, with the highest abundance measured near to the coast and in the southern part of the area, downstream Chioggia inlet. Similarly to what observed for beach litter, the main source for seabed litter is represented by public activities (domestic and touristic waste). Instead, the second most important sources are sea-based: shipping and fishing, ranking as second and third most represented sources respectively.

This review offers several useful concepts in the assessment of sources to be used in numerical modelling and in the evaluation of their uncertain. The data analysis underlines that in the same station a high heterogeneity of ML typologies is found, together with high variability in the abundance of each typology. This is due to the transport pattern, which varies with seasons and with the meteo-marine conditions, modifying consequently the ML composition and abundance in the same place. Another factor influencing heterogeneity and abundance of ML in a station is the temporal variability of ML sources. Human activities acting as sources of ML have a strong seasonal and temporal variation and this means that a correct model should consider this temporal variation to correctly reproduce the ML distribution. Unfortunately, measuring the temporal variation of ML sources is an hard challenge in data collection so we can assume this as uncertain factor in the evaluation of modelling results.

Another relevant aspect for the modelling realization is the strong local character of the ML composition. The distribution of ML in different stations shows a strong local

MAELSTROM

influence. The spatial variability of ML composition and abundance is very evident and indicates the high relevance in the source locations. Correct positioning of the ML sources is crucial to reproduce the final ML pattern, overall working on a small basin scale. This important information has to be estimated, merging spatially explicit information on the characteristics and the use of the territory and adopting the distribution of human activities as proxy for ML sources. When evaluating the source location, human behaviour should also be considered, i.e. voluntary discharge of fishing material, which influences in an unpredictable way the final ML distribution.

Rivers need special attention when they have to be included in models. Despite a scarce quantitative knowledge of rivers as input of ML, they integrate the amount of ML coming from the watershed and from cities and towns. Recent studies in this review indicate that the relationship between discharge and amount of transported ML is not linear and often small urban rivers are the most polluting ones. This indicates as good modelling practice to include in numerical model not only the rivers most relevant in discharge terms, but also, working on local scale, the rivers flowing through important urban settlements, regardless their discharge.

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Annexes

See the supplementary information in the documents Annex1 and Annex2 reporting respectively the relation between IT and G categories and the beach data in the Venice study area, and reporting the seabed data in Venice study area.

ANNEX 1

Litter classification

Table 1. Relationship between IT categories and G categories based on item description used for the monitoring of beach litter.

IT Categories	Description	G Categories	Description
<i>Material: Plastic</i>			
IT1	Bags, shopping bags, garbage bags / small plastic bags, e.g. freezer bags / Plastic bag ends from pull off plastic bags / fragments of plastic sheets	G3	Bags, shopping bags, garbage bags
		G4	Small plastic bags, e.g. freezer bags
		G5	Plastic bag ends from pull off plastic bags
		G25	Tobacco pouches / plastic cigarette box packaging
IT2	Cleaner bottles and containers / Beach use related cosmetic bottles and containers, eg. Sunblocks / Other cosmetics bottles & containers	G9	Cleaner bottles & containers
		G11	Beach use related cosmetic bottles and containers, eg. Sunblocks
		G12	Other cosmetics bottles and containers
IT3	Other bottles and engine oil bottles	G13	Other bottles & containers
		G14	Engine oil bottles & containers <50 cm
		G15	Engine oil bottles & containers > 50 cm
IT4	Car and motorcycle parts	G19	Car parts
IT5	Cigarette lighters	G26	Cigarette lighters
IT6	Pens and pen lids	G28	Pens and pen lids
IT7	Cups and cup lids / Cutlery and trays / Straws and stirrers Plastic rings from bottle caps / lids / Crisps packets/sweets wrappers / Plastic caps/lids chemicals, detergents / Plastic caps/lids unidentified /	G33	Cups and cup lids
		G34	Cutlery and trays
		G35	Straws and stirrers
		G24	Plastic rings from bottle caps/lids

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	Drink bottles / 4/6-pack yokes, six-pack rings / Plastic caps/lids drinks / Food containers incl. fast food containers	G30	Crisps packets/sweets wrappers
		G22	Plastic caps/lids chemicals, detergents (non-food)
		G23	Plastic caps/lids unidentified
		G7	Drink bottles <=0.5l
		G8	Drink bottles >0.5l
		G1	4/6-pack yokes, six-pack rings
		G21	Plastic caps/lids drinks
		G10	Food containers incl. fast food containers
IT8	Gloves (industrial/professional rubber gloves) / Gloves (washing up)	G41	Gloves (industrial/professional rubber gloves)
		G40	Gloves (washing up)
IT9	Floats for fishing nets / Buoys / Fenders	G62	Floats for fishing nets
		G63	Buoys
		G64	Fenders
IT10	Strapping bands / Toilet fresheners	G66	Strapping bands
		G93	Toilet fresheners
IT11	Combs / hair brushes / sunglasses / Shoes and sandals / Flip-flops	G29	Combs/hair brushes/sunglasses
		G71	Shoes/sandals
		G102	Flip-flops
IT12	Foam sponge / Fertiliser and animal feed bags / Mesh vegetable bags / Sheets, industrial packaging, plastic sheeting / Fibre glass and fragments / Hard hats/Helmets	G36	Fertiliser/animal feed bags
		G37	Mesh vegetable bags
		G67	Sheets, industrial packaging, plastic sheeting
		G68	Fibre glass/fragments
		G69	Hard hats/Helmets
		G73	Foam sponge
IT13	CD, CD-box / Toys and party poppers / Light sticks	G32	Toys and party poppers
		G60	Light sticks (tubes with fluid) incl. packaging

	(tubes with fluid) incl. packaging	G84	CD, CD-box
IT14	Jerry cans (square plastic containers with handle) / Crates and containers / baskets / Buckets / Plastic flower pots	G16	Jerry cans (square plastic containers with handle)
		G18	Crates and containers / baskets
		G65	Buckets
		G90	Plastic flower pots
IT15	Fish boxes - expanded polystyrene	G58	Fish boxes - expanded polystyrene
IT16	Rope / String and Cords / nets and net pieces / Fish boxes / Fishing lines / Bait containers and packaging	G49	Rope (diameter more than 1cm)
		G50	String and cord (diameter less than 1cm)
		G53	Nets and pieces of net < 50 cm
		G54	Nets and pieces of net > 50cm
		G56	Tangled nets/cord
		G57	Fish boxes - plastic
		G59	Fishing line/monofilament (angling)
		G92	Bait containers/packaging
IT17	Crab and lobster pots and tops / Tags / Octopus pots / Mussels nets, Oyster nets / Oyster trays (round from oyster cultures) / Plastic sheeting from mussel culture	G42	Crab/lobster pots and tops
		G43	Tags (fishing and industry)
		G44	Octopus pots
		G45	Mussels nets, Oyster nets
		G46	Oyster trays (round from oyster cultures)
		G47	Plastic sheeting from mussel culture
IT18	Other polystyrene items	G82	Polystyrene pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm
		G83	Polystyrene pieces > 50 cm
IT19	Other plastic items on fragments	G79	Plastic pieces 2,5 cm > < 50cm
		G80	Plastic pieces > 50 cm

		G87	Masking tape
		G89	plastic construction waste
		G124	Other plastic items (identifiable)
Material: Rubber			
IT20	Balloons and balloon sticks	G125	Balloons and balloon sticks
IT21	Rubber boots	G127	Rubber boots
IT22	Tyres and belts	G128	Tyres and belts
IT23	Rubber bands	G131	Rubber bands
IT24	Other rubber pieces	G134	Other rubber pieces
Material: Textiles			
IT25	Sacking (hessian) / Carpet & Furnishing	G140	Sacking (hessian)
		G141	Carpet & Furnishing
IT26	Clothing (clothes, shoes) / Backpacks & bags	G137	Clothing (clothes, shoes)
		G138	Shoes
		G139	Backpacks & bags
IT27	Other textiles / Rope, string and nets	G142	Rope, string and nets
		G145	Other textiles (incl. rags)
Material: Paper and Cardboard			
IT28	Paper bags	G147	Paper bags
IT29	Cardboard / Newspapers & magazines / Paper fragments	G148	Cardboard (boxes & fragments)
		G154	Newspapers & magazines
		G156	Paper fragments
IT30	Tetrapack / Paper cups, food trays, food wrappers, drink containers	G150	Cartons/Tetrapack Milk
		G151	Cartons/Tetrapack (others)
		G153	Paper cups, food trays, food wrappers, drink containers

IT31	Cigarette packets	G152	Cigarette packets
IT32	Cigarette butts	G27	Cigarette butts
IT33	Other paper items	G158	Other paper items
Material: Wood			
IT34	Corks	G159	Corks
IT35	Crates and boxes	G162	Crates
		G164	Fish boxes
IT36	Ice-cream sticks, chip forks, chopsticks, toothpicks	G165	Ice-cream sticks, chip forks, chopsticks, toothpicks
IT37	Pallets / Wood (processed) / Other wood	G160	Pallets
		G161	Wood (processed)
		G171	Other wood <50 cm
		G172	Other wood > 50 cm
Material: Metals			
IT38	Aerosol/Spray cans industry	G174	Aerosol/Spray cans industry
IT39	Cans (beverage) / Cans (food) / Foil wrappers, aluminum foil / Bottle caps, lids & pull tabs / Disposable BBQ's / Other cans (< 4 L)	G175	Cans (beverage)
		G176	Cans (food)
		G177	Foil wrappers, aluminum foil
		G178	Bottle caps, lids & pull tabs
		G179	Disposable BBQ's
		G188	Other cans (< 4 L)
IT40	Appliances (refrigerators, washers, etc.) / Car parts / batteries	G180	Appliances (refrigerators, washers, etc.)
		G193	Car parts / batteries
IT41	Fishing related (weights, sinkers, lures, hooks)	G182	Fishing related (weights, sinkers, lures, hooks)
IT42	Industrial scrap	G186	Industrial scrap
IT43	Drums, e.g. oil / Gas bottles, drums & buckets	G187	Drums, e.g. oil
		G189	Gas bottles, drums & buckets (> 4 L)
IT44	Paint tins	G190	Paint tins
IT45	Wire, wire mesh, barbed wire	G191	Wire, wire mesh, barbed wire

MAELSTROM

IT46	Household Batteries	G195	Household Batteries
IT47	Other metal items / fragments	G194	Cables
		G198	Other metal pieces < 50 cm
		G199	Other metal pieces > 50 cm
Material: Glass / Ceramics			
IT48	Bottles / Tableware (plates & cups)	G200	Bottles
		G203	Tableware (plates & cups)
IT49	Light bulbs / Fluorescent light tubes	G202	Light bulbs
		G205	Fluorescent light tubes
IT50	Construction material (brick, cement, pipes)	G204	Construction material (brick, cement, pipes)
IT51	Glass or ceramic fragments / Other glass items	G208	Glass or ceramic fragments > 2,5 cm
		G210	Other glass items
Material: Sanitary waste			
IT52	Condoms	G133	Condoms
IT53	Cotton bud sticks	G95	Cotton bud sticks
IT54	Sanitary towels/panty liners/backing strips / Diapers/nappies	G96	Sanitary towels/panty liners/backing strips
		G98	Diapers/nappies
Material: Medical waste			
IT55	Other sanitary items	-	-
IT56	Medical/Pharmaceuticals containers/tubes	G100	Medical/Pharmaceuticals containers/tubes
IT57	Other medical items (swabs, bandaging etc.)	G99	Other medical items (swabs, bandaging etc.)
IT58	Other medical items (swabs, bandaging etc.)	G211	Other medical items (swabs, bandaging etc.)
Material: Faeces			
IT59	Dog faeces bag	G101	Dog faeces bag

Table 2. Full list of indicator-items used for monitoring programmes and relative attributed sources (MCS – Marine Conservation Society (2013)).

Source	Indicator-items
<i>Public Litter</i>	4/6 pack yokes, plastic bags (including supermarket), plastic drinks bottles, plastic food containers, plastic toiletries bottles, plastic caps / lids, cigarette lighters / tobacco pouches, combs / hair brushes / sunglasses, crisp / sweet / lolly / sandwich wrappers, cutlery / trays / straws / cups, pens, plastic shoes / sandals, shotgun cartridges, toys / party poppers / fireworks / dummies, polystyrene fast food containers / cups, balloons / balloon string, clothing / shoes / beach towels, disposable barbecues, metal bottle caps, metal drink cans, foil wrappers, household batteries, animal faeces in bags, animal faeces not in bags, paper bags, cartons / tetrapak (e.g. fruit juice), cigarette packets, cigarette stubs, paper cups, newspapers / magazines, corks, ice lolly sticks / chip forks, glass bottles, glass pieces.
<i>Fishing</i>	Fish boxes, fishing line, fishing net and net pieces <50cm, fishing net and net pieces >50cm, floats (fishing buoys) / reels, plastic lobster / crab pots and tops, string and cord diameter <1cm, polystyrene buoys, polystyrene fish boxes, rubber boots, heavy duty gloves, tyres with holes, fishing weights / hooks / lures, metal lobster / crab pots and tops, wood lobster / crab pots and tops.
<i>Sewage-Related Debris</i>	Condoms, cotton bud sticks, nappies, tampon applicators / tampons, toilet fresheners, towels / panty liners / plastic backing strips, wet wipes, other sanitary items.
<i>Shipping</i>	Plastic cleaner bottles, foreign plastic bottles, plastic oil bottles, industrial packaging / crates / sheeting, mesh bags (e.g. vegetable), Rope diameter >1 cm, strapping bands, aerosol cans, metal food cans, oil drums, cartons / purepak (e.g. milk), pallets / crates, light bulbs / tubes.
<i>Fly Tipped</i>	Traffic cones, tyres without holes / wheels, cloth furnishings, car parts / car batteries, scrap metal / appliances / paint tins, pottery / ceramic.
<i>Medical</i>	Inhalers, plasters, syringes, other medical items.
<i>Non-Sourced</i>	Plastic pieces <2.5cm, plastic pieces >2.5cm, other plastics, fibreglass, foam / sponge / insulation, polystyrene packaging, polystyrene pieces <50cm, other polystyrene items, light weight gloves, rubber pieces <50cm, other rubber items, cloth pieces, sacking, other cloth items, wire / wire mesh / metal pieces, other metal items, cardboard, other paper items, paint brushes, wood pieces (not twigs), other wood items.

Table 3. Relation between IT and G categories, their possible sources and materials.

IT categories	G categories	Sources	Materials
IT1	G3, G4, G5, G25	Public litter	Plastic
IT2	G9, G11, G12	Public litter	Plastic
IT3	G13, G14, G15	Fly Tipped	Plastic
IT4	G19	Fly Tipped	Plastic
IT5	G26	Public litter	Plastic
IT6	G28	Public litter	Plastic
IT7	G33, G34, G35, G24, G30, G22, G23, G7, G8, G1, G21, G10	Public litter	Plastic

IT8	G41, G40, G31	Non-Sourced	Plastic
IT9	G62, G63, G64	Fishing	Plastic
IT10	G66, G93	Public litter	Plastic
IT11	G29, G71, G102	Public litter	Plastic
IT12	G36, G37, G67, G68, G69, G73	Non-Sourced	Plastic
IT13	G32, G60, G84	Public litter	Plastic
IT14	G16, G18, G65, G90	Public litter	Plastic
IT15	G58	Fishing	Plastic
IT16	G49, G50, G53, G54, G56, G57, G59, G92	Fishing	Plastic
IT17	G42, G43, G44, G45, G46, G47	Fishing	Plastic
IT18	G82, G83	Non-Sourced	Plastic
IT19	G79, G80, G87, G124	Non-Sourced	Plastic
IT20	G125	Public litter	Plastic
IT21	G127	Fishing	Plastic
IT22	G128	Fly Tipped	Plastic
IT23	G131	Public litter	Plastic
IT24	G134	Non-Sourced	Plastic
IT25	G140, G141	Non-Sourced	Mixed
IT26	G137, G138, G139	Public litter	Mixed
IT27	G142, G145	Non-Sourced	Mixed
IT28	G147	Non-Sourced	Paper
IT29	G148, G154, G156	Public litter	Paper
IT30	G150, G151, G153	Public litter	Paper
IT31	G152	Public litter	Paper
IT32	G27	Public litter	Paper
IT33	G158	Public litter	Paper
IT34	G159	Public litter	Wood
IT35	G162, G164	Fishing	Wood
IT36	G165	Public litter	Wood
IT37	G160, G161, G171, G172	Public litter	Wood
IT38	G174	Shipping	Metal
IT39	G175, G176, G177, G178, G179, G188	Public litter	Metal
IT40	G180, G193	Fly Tipped	Metal
IT41	G182	Fishing	Metal
IT42	G186	Fly Tipped	Metal
IT43	G187, G189	Fly Tipped	Metal
IT44	G190	Fly Tipped	Metal
IT45	G191	Non-Sourced	Metal
IT46	G195	Public litter	Metal
IT47	G194, G198, G199	Non-Sourced	Metal
IT48	G200, G203	Public litter	Glass / Ceramic
IT49	G202, G205	Public litter	Glass / Ceramic

IT50	G204	Public litter	Glass / Ceramic
IT51	G208, G210	Non-Sourced	Glass / Ceramic
IT52	G133	Sewage-Related Debris	Mixed
IT53	G95	Sewage-Related Debris	Mixed
IT54	G96, G98	Sewage-Related Debris	Mixed
IT55		Sewage-Related Debris	Mixed
IT56	G100	Medical	Mixed
IT57	G99	Medical	Mixed
IT58	G211	Medical	Mixed
IT59	G101	Public litter	Mixed

Beach litter in Venice

Table 4a. The total number of items found in the beaches of Lido, Hospital, Lido S. Nicolò, Pellestrina and Lazzaretto at each sampling period (n. of items / 100 m).

	Lido - Hospital			Lido - S. Nicolò			Pellestrina	Lazzaretto
	2019-03-16	2019-12-06	2020-02-13	2019-03-16	2019-12-06	2020-02-13	2019-12-12	2021-04-24
IT1	79	29	31	90	70	21	13	90
IT2	3	0	1	9	2	2	1	9
IT3	1	0	0	2	7	0	1	2
IT4	2	0	0	1	3	0	0	1
IT5	0	0	1	2	2	1	0	2
IT6	0	0	5	2	108	4	2	2
IT7	146	18	93	211	20	143	51	211
IT8	0	0	6	10	1	2	0	10
IT9	0	0	1	1	6	1	1	1
IT10	6	0	3	3	7	1	2	3
IT11	0	0	5	1	10	0	0	1
IT12	27	0	9	8	6	10	1	8
IT13	2	0	0	6	1	11	1	6
IT14	2	1	6	3	25	0	1	3
IT15	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0
IT16	18	1	19	25	2	13	3	25
IT17	43	1	5	31	534	11	20	31
IT18	16	3	28	31	1	9	14	31
IT19	37	13	305	206	0	582	84	206
IT20	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
IT21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

MAELSTROM

IT22	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
IT23	0	1	1	2	11	6	0	2
IT24	2	7	7	2	27	19	2	2
IT25	0	0	1	1	3	6	1	1
IT26	0	0	2	6	3	10	0	6
IT27	2	1	16	13	35	27	3	13
IT28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT29	5	0	0	4	3	1	0	4
IT30	0	0	0	4	1	0	0	4
IT31	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	3
IT32	0	0	0	4	9	1	0	4
IT33	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	3
IT34	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
IT35	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
IT36	0	1	1	0	4	8	0	0
IT37	1	3	4	17	5	2	0	17
IT38	0	0	0	0	0	20	0	0
IT39	2	0	6	11	21	0	1	11
IT40	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT41	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT42	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
IT43	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
IT44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT45	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0
IT46	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
IT47	1	3	1	3	6	0	6	0
IT48	16	83	20	72	24	4	2	72
IT49	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
IT50	0	340	204	92	47	10	0	92
IT51	8	53	134	128	169	17	2	128
IT52	1	0	1	1	3	1	1	1
IT53	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
IT54	0	0	0	3	5	3	0	3
IT55	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT56	1	0	1	4	8	1	0	4
IT57	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
IT58	0	0	6	0	12	0	0	0
IT59	1	0	0	2	5	2	0	2
Total	429	559	926	1021	1229	953	213	1018

Table 4b. The total number of items found in the beach of Brussa at each sampling period (n. of items / 100 m).

	Brussa									
	2015-10-20	2015-10-22	2016-03-29	2016-03-31	2016-10-19	2016-10-31	2017-02-15	2017-10-09	2018-03-26	2018-10-17
IT1	22	13	6	41	30	10	23	1	16	2
IT2	2	9	0	11	11	4	0	1	2	1
IT3	0	1	0	1	0	0	3	0	0	0
IT4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT5	10	0	0	4	6	3	0	1	2	0
IT6	1	1	3	6	4	1	1	0	2	1
IT7	142	237	26	275	413	160	119	26	124	39
IT8	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	0	2	0
IT9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT10	1	2	0	2	4	1	5	0	4	1
IT11	0	0	0	1	2	2	4	0	5	0
IT12	7	20	6	37	9	11	37	1	4	20
IT13	13	18	0	8	18	7	8	0	9	3
IT14	0	2	0	1	1	0	1	0	6	0
IT15	0	1	0	1	1	3	1	0	0	2
IT16	5	5	6	22	11	25	2	2	12	22
IT17	7	62	0	118	9	186	14	5	5	3
IT18	31	22	6	21	64	71	16	5	17	21
IT19	85	89	22	98	180	132	134	41	109	180
IT20	10	7	0	6	12	0	2	0	2	3
IT21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT23	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
IT24	1	2	0	2	1	3	0	0	0	0
IT25	1	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	1	1
IT26	0	0	0	4	2	1	0	0	1	2
IT27	10	1	2	12	5	6	2	4	1	16
IT28	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	4	1
IT29	4	0	1	2	12	5	2	3	0	15
IT30	0	2	0	1	8	3	1	0	1	1
IT31	3	0	0	3	2	2	2	0	0	1
IT32	134	8	2	16	983	66	109	66	0	134
IT33	5	2	2	16	3	5	2	9	0	0
IT34	4	0	0	3	4	7	0	1	2	0
IT35	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT36	4	1	0	0	8	1	1	0	1	12
IT37	0	0	0	0	2	5	0	0	0	0
IT38	1	0	0	1	5	1	0	0	0	0
IT39	2	3	0	21	6	5	7	1	0	9

IT40	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT41	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0
IT42	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
IT43	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
IT45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
IT46	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT47	0	24	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
IT48	0	3	2	3	0	1	0	0	1	0
IT49	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
IT50	0	0	0	3	1	5	1	3	14	5
IT51	1	1	4	1	5	0	36	3	23	3
IT52	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT53	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	16	32
IT54	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
IT55	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	1	1
IT56	4	1	0	2	2	2	1	0	0	2
IT57	2	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	0	0
IT58	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
IT59	0	0	0	3	0	2	0	0	1	0
Total	515	540	90	752	1833	740	540	179	395	537

Table 4c. The total number of items found in the beach of Cavallino at each sampling period (n. of items / 100 m).

	Cavallino					
	2017-02-16	2017-02-20	2017-10-06	2018-03-20	2018-04-24	2018-10-10
IT1	102	0	13	82	12	39
IT2	16	9	0	25	9	7
IT3	0	4	0	2	0	0
IT4	0	0	0	0	1	0
IT5	10	1	4	14	4	7
IT6	5	5	0	14	4	3
IT7	304	117	61	1007	273	299
IT8	2	0	0	6	0	0
IT9	0	0	0	2	0	0
IT10	8	0	0	26	3	0
IT11	4	0	0	10	6	2
IT12	29	11	0	158	13	10
IT13	16	9	3	52	6	14
IT14	4	0	1	6	15	0
IT15	2	0	0	0	4	1
IT16	57	1	4	92	14	44
IT17	475	1	54	561	38	57

MAELSTROM

IT18	62	31	53	253	138	77
IT19	308	86	118	660	176	569
IT20	2	2	3	6	1	11
IT21	1	0	0	0	0	0
IT22	0	0	0	0	1	0
IT23	0	0	0	0	0	5
IT24	7	6	1	5	1	2
IT25	0	0	0	2	0	1
IT26	1	0	0	1	2	0
IT27	36	1	16	5	2	32
IT28	4	0	1	0	1	1
IT29	0	0	25	1	2	1
IT30	2	0	1	4	8	0
IT31	1	0	1	66	3	7
IT32	6	0	134	4	7	371
IT33	11	1	0	0	9	26
IT34	6	0	0	2	1	4
IT35	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT36	2	0	5	0	1	14
IT37	6	7	0	7	12	50
IT38	1	0	0	2	2	1
IT39	12	0	6	14	5	27
IT40	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT41	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT42	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT43	1	2	0	0	2	0
IT44	0	0	0	1	0	0
IT45	2	1	0	0	0	3
IT46	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT47	1	1	0	1	0	2
IT48	4	5	0	3	9	1
IT49	1	0	0	0	1	0
IT50	1	0	1	0	0	1
IT51	3	0	2	2	11	7
IT52	1	0	0	1	0	0
IT53	0	30	21	212	37	298
IT54	1	0	0	5	17	1
IT55	1	3	0	7	4	2
IT56	3	2	0	5	8	16
IT57	1	0	0	4	0	2
IT58	0	0	0	4	0	1
IT59	1	0	0	2	1	0
Total	1523	336	528	3336	864	2016

Table 4d. The total number of items found in the beach of Chioggia - Sottomarina at each sampling period (n. of items / 100 m).

	Chioggia - Sottomarina								
	2015-10-20	2016-03-29	2016-10-19	2017-02-15	2017-02-20	2017-10-09	2017-10-12	2018-03-26	2018-10-17
IT1	13	3	1	12	19	1	3	4	5
IT2	1	0	0	0	29	1	4	0	0
IT3	0	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0
IT4	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
IT5	0	0	0	0	6	0	3	1	0
IT6	1	1	0	0	2	0	4	0	0
IT7	21	8	71	59	244	14	73	38	53
IT8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT10	0	0	0	1	4	0	6	0	0
IT11	0	0	1	1	5	0	0	1	0
IT12	4	4	0	3	3	2	1	1	12
IT13	1	0	0	2	7	0	6	0	0
IT14	0	0	0	1	6	0	0	0	1
IT15	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
IT16	1	3	5	1	9	1	15	3	8
IT17	3	0	0	10	10	5	6	2	0
IT18	19	3	16	11	105	3	5	8	4
IT19	12	12	31	67	170	9	185	17	44
IT20	2	0	1	0	6	0	0	2	2
IT21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT22	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0
IT23	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
IT24	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
IT25	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3
IT26	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0
IT27	2	1	1	1	1	2	7	0	0
IT28	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
IT29	1	1	8	0	1	0	5	0	0
IT30	0	0	0	0	1	0	4	2	0
IT31	2	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	5
IT32	28	2	526	99	9	53	88	10	334
IT33	2	2	2	1	3	9	0	1	0
IT34	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	0
IT35	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT36	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
IT37	0	0	0	0	8	0	1	1	0
IT38	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
IT39	0	0	1	5	0	0	13	1	3

IT40	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT41	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT42	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT43	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
IT46	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT47	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
IT48	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
IT49	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
IT50	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
IT51	0	0	0	10	2	0	2	1	0
IT52	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT53	0	0	0	0	40	0	94	11	12
IT54	0	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	1
IT55	0	0	0	1	3	0	1	0	1
IT56	1	0	0	1	9	0	3	0	1
IT57	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
IT58	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
IT59	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Total	117	40	668	293	719	103	537	107	501

Table 4e. The total number of items found in the beach of Barricata at each sampling period (n. of items / 100 m).

	Barricata					
	2019-03-14	2019-03-26	2019-10-22	2019-10-23	2019-10-31	2019-11-18
IT1	26	66	4	8	1	31
IT2	5	29	2	0	14	2
IT3	0	5	0	0	0	0
IT4	0	2	0	0	1	0
IT5	3	27	0	2	17	7
IT6	0	9	2	0	9	4
IT7	44	452	38	63	195	95
IT8	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT9	0	3	0	0	0	0
IT10	2	9	0	5	5	4
IT11	0	10	0	0	4	10
IT12	0	14	5	2	46	6
IT13	1	15	0	2	16	1
IT14	0	24	0	0	10	0
IT15	4	4	0	0	1	0
IT16	0	19	1	1	1	7
IT17	0	79	0	0	11	9

IT18	28	64	63	28	247	38
IT19	56	751	51	143	385	111
IT20	2	9	1	0	2	2
IT21	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT22	1	0	0	0	0	0
IT23	0	0	0	0	1	0
IT24	0	16	0	0	1	3
IT25	0	1	0	0	1	0
IT26	1	1	1	0	0	0
IT27	2	14	2	7	16	7
IT28	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT29	1	1	0	0	0	1
IT30	1	8	0	0	0	0
IT31	0	2	1	3	0	0
IT32	3	10	128	77	328	2
IT33	1	3	5	3	0	1
IT34	0	1	2	0	3	2
IT35	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT36	1	0	0	2	4	1
IT37	3	13	1	2	6	1
IT38	0	3	1	0	2	0
IT39	1	13	2	5	9	0
IT40	0	1	0	0	0	1
IT41	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT42	0	1	0	0	0	0
IT43	0	1	0	0	0	0
IT44	0	1	0	0	0	0
IT45	0	2	0	1	2	0
IT46	0	1	0	0	0	0
IT47	0	0	0	1	3	0
IT48	1	9	1	1	14	0
IT49	0	0	0	0	0	0
IT50	24	12	1	36	3	26
IT51	32	21	0	1	1	24
IT52	0	1	0	0	0	1
IT53	14	268	13	14	188	33
IT54	1	11	0	0	0	1
IT55	2	3	0	0	5	0
IT56	2	7	0	0	13	3
IT57	0	5	0	1	3	0
IT58	0	1	1	1	2	2
IT59	0	3	0	0	0	0
Total	262	2025	326	409	1564	430

ANNEX 2

Seabed litter in the Venetian coastal area

Table 1. Relation between IT and G categories, their possible sources and materials.

G category	Description	Sources
G2	Bags	Public litter
G6	Bottles	Public litter
G10	Food containers incl. fast food containers	Public litter
G18	Crates and containers / baskets	Fishing
G20	Plastic caps and lids	Public litter
G27	Cigarette butts and filters	Public litter
G39	Gloves	Fishing
G45	Mussels nets, Oyster nets	Fishing
G48	Synthetic rope	Shipping
G51	Fishing net	Fishing
G61	Other fishing related	Fishing
G66	Strapping bands	Shipping
G67	Sheets, industrial packaging, plastic sheeting	Shipping
G79	Plastic pieces 2.5 cm > < 50cm	Non-sourced
G93	Cable ties	Non-sourced
G96	Sanitary towels/panty liners/backing strips	Sewage-Related Debris
G98	Diapers/nappies	Sewage-Related Debris
G124	Other plastic/polystyrene items (identifiable)	Non-sourced
G125	Balloons and balloon sticks	Public litter
G127	Rubber boot	Fishing
G128	Tyres and belts	Fly tipped
G132	Bobbins (fishing)	Fishing
G133	Condoms (incl. packaging)	Sewage-Related Debris
G134	Other rubber pieces	Non-Sourced
G136	Shoes	Public litter
G137	Clothing / rags (clothing, hats, towel)	Public litter
G141	Carpet & Furnishing	Fly tipped

G142	Rope, string and nets	Fishing
G145	Other textiles (incl. rags)	Fly tipped
G146	paper/Cardboard	Non-sourced
G148	Cardboard (boxes & fragments)	Non-sourced
G158	Other paper items	Non-sourced
G170	Wood (processed)	Non-sourced
G173	Other (specify)	Non-sourced
G175	Cans (beverage)	Public litter
G176	Cans (food)	Fishing
G182	Fishing related (weights, sinkers, lurhooks)	Fishing
G185	Middle size containers	Non-sourced
G187	Drums, e.g. oil	Shipping
G194	Cables	Non-sourced
G197	Other (metal)	Non-sourced
G200	Bottles incl. pieces	Public litter
G201	Jars incl. pieces	Public litter
G208	Glass or ceramic fragments >2.5cm	Fly tipped

Table 2a. The total number of items found in the 1-8 stations (n. of items / haul).

	Station							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
G10	12	30	27	6	28	10	4	20
G124	0	6	1	0	0	1	0	2
G125	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G127	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
G128	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
G132	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G133	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G134	0	0	1	0	2	0	2	8
G136	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
G137	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
G141	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
G142	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	1
G145	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
G146	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G148	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G158	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G170	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G173	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G175	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0
G176	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G182	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G185	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G187	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G194	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
G197	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
G2	6	20	7	7	6	1	1	2
G20	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
G200	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G208	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
G27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G39	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
G45	9	2	2	4	1	2	1	69
G48	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
G51	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
G6	3	6	0	3	7	1	0	0
G61	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2
G66	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G67	23	44	23	6	18	7	6	7

G79	0	6	0	0	5	0	0	3
G93	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G96	5	8	4	1	2	0	0	0
G98	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	58	123	67	33	74	29	18	118

Table 2b. The total number of items found in the 9-16 stations (n. of items / haul).

	Station							
	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
G10	0	4	2	0	2	2	2	3
G124	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	1
G125	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G127	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G128	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G132	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G133	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G134	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
G136	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G137	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
G141	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G142	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
G145	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
G146	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G148	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G158	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G170	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G173	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G175	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
G176	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G182	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
G185	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G187	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
G194	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
G197	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G2	2	2	0	0	0	3	1	3
G20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G200	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G208	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G39	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G45	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	0
G48	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G51	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	2
G6	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2

G61	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
G66	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G67	5	5	0	12	2	1	1	3
G79	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
G93	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
G96	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
G98	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	10	17	5	16	9	10	7	22

Table 2c. The total number of items found in the 17-24 stations (n. of items / haul).

	Station							
	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
G10	1	0	1	0	0	2	1	2
G124	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G125	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G127	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G128	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G132	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G133	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G134	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
G136	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G137	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G141	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G142	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
G145	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G146	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G148	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
G158	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
G170	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	2
G173	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G175	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
G176	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G182	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G185	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
G187	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G194	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G197	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G2	1	1	0	0	1	0	2	4
G20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G200	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G201	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
G208	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1
G27	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
G39	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G45	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	0
G48	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G51	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G6	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1

G61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G66	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G67	7	8	0	2	2	6	8	5
G79	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	2
G93	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0
G96	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
G98	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total	17	11	8	4	7	11	18	21

Table 2d. The total number of items found in the 25-32 stations (n. of items / haul).

	Station							
	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
G10	4	21	17	6	5	1	8	6
G124	0	1	3	1	0	2	1	2
G125	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G127	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G128	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
G132	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
G133	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
G134	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
G136	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
G137	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
G141	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G142	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
G145	0	0	1	0	0	0	4	0
G146	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G148	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G158	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1
G170	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G173	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G175	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
G176	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
G18	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0
G182	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G185	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
G187	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

G194	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G197	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0
G2	1	2	1	6	0	1	6	2
G20	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
G200	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
G201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G208	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
G39	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
G45	11	12	4	4	3	0	62	0
G48	1	0	2	1	2	0	1	0
G51	2	0	0	0	0	0	3	0
G6	4	6	4	0	0	0	2	2
G61	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
G66	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
G67	9	24	24	7	4	6	6	3
G79	2	10	8	3	0	2	7	0
G93	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G96	3	12	5	1	1	1	1	2
G98	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	37	91	77	32	15	16	111	24